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California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
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PATIENT EDUCATION PROGRAM DEVELOPMENT: NON-PHARMACOLOGICAL
INTERVENTIONS FOR MANAGEMENT OF CHRONIC BACK PAIN

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: Quality improvement (QI) project designed to implement and evaluate a patient education program, with non-pharmacological interventions (NPI) for treating chronic low back pain (CLBP). The aim was to assess changes in knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs about NPIs after receiving CLBP education. **Background:** Chronic low back pain is the leading cause of disability worldwide. Opioids are commonly used for CLBP. Multimodal approaches for treating CLBP are more effective than unimodal treatments. The Health Promotion Model guided this project. **Methodology:** This QI project used an interventional pretest-posttest design. The project was implemented at a private clinic in San Bernardino County. Thirty adults with CLBP participated and completed a Pain, Enjoyment, and General Activity scale (PEG), Low Back Pain Questionnaire (LKQ), and a Survey of Pain Attitudes (SOPA) at the start and end of the project. Education on CLBP and NPIs was provided through a pamphlet and motivational interviewing. Patients were contacted twice weekly to obtain data and motivate the use of NPIs. **Results:** Demographics represented the clinic population. Special cause variations showed an increase in NPI use, decrease in pain interference with the enjoyment of life (PIwEOL), and general activity (PIwGA). No change in opiates and attitudes. Paired t-tests showed a significant decrease in pre- and post-surveys for pain, PIwEOL and PIwGA ($p = .009$), and LKQ ($p < .001$). No significant changes in pain attitudes or opiates noted. **Discussion:** Educational intervention increased knowledge and NPIs use. Pain level, PIwEOL, and PIwGA decreased. **Recommendations for practice change** addressed patient education and the use of NPIs.

Keywords: Non-pharmacological interventions, pain level, opioids

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Background

Pain is a medical condition that can have lasting negative effects on the lives of people who experience it (Dart et al., 2015; Dueñas et al., 2016). The pain can be chronic or high-impact chronic pain. Chronic pain (CP) is an unpleasant emotional or physical sensation that persists beyond normal tissue healing and lasts more than three months (International Association for the Study of Pain [IASP], 2017). According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2019) in 2016, 20.4% of adults in the U.S. lived with CP, while 8% lived with high-impact chronic pain (HICP). High-impact chronic pain is CP that is accompanied by restrictions of major life activities, such as going to work or school (National Center for Complementary and Integrative Health [NCCIH], 2018). Patients living with HICP also reported higher levels of pain and tended to have more comorbidities, such as anxiety and depression, compared to patients with CP (NCCIH, 2018).

Although CP can affect any part of the body, the lower back is the most common location (Deyo et al., 2015; Maher et al., 2017; Stump et al., 2016). Approximately 80% of adults will suffer from lower back pain at some point in their lifetime (National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke [NINDS], 2019). Low back pain is responsible for about 10.7% of disability and time lost from work a year (NINDS, 2019).

Low back pain is felt in the region between the lower ribs and the upper gluteal muscles (Baronet et al., 2016; NINDS, 2020). Chronic low back pain (CLBP) is described in two ways: identifiable pathology, such as from injury due to a fall; or unidentifiable pathology with no specific cause (Bardin et al., 2017; Deyo et al., 2015; Stump et al., 2016). Unidentifiable pathology accounts for more than 90% of all low back pain cases (Bardin et al., 2017; Herndon et al., 2015; Maher et al., 2016; NINDS, 2020). Chronic low back pain can be radiating or

localized (NINDS, 2020; Stump et al., 2016). Radiating pain is either referred, radicular or neuropathic (Stump et al., 2016). Referred pain originates from muscle tension. Radicular pain results from compression of spinal structures, such as a herniated vertebral disk, and follows the path of a nerve, such as the sciatic (Allegrì et al., 2016; Stump et al., 2016). When neurological symptoms, such as numbness accompanying radicular pain, it is referred to as radiculopathy (Allegrì et al., 2016). Neuropathic back pain results from disease or injury to the nervous system and is associated with HICP (Stump et al., 2016).

Patients who experience chronic back pain often seek treatment, the most prevalent of which is the use of opioids (Bardin et al., 2017; Dart et al., 2016; Deyo et al., 2015; Maher et al., 2017; Shah et al., 2017). This pattern has led to many patients taking high doses of opioids (CDC, 2019; Dart et al., 2016; Deyo et al., 2015). Approximately 3% to 4% of adults in the U.S. are taking prescription opioids for CP relief (CDC, 2016). When a patient takes opioids over a long period, the patient will require more and more medication to achieve the same level of pain relief (CDC, 2019b; Dueñas et al., 2016; Ray et al., 2016; Shah et al., 2017). This is referred to as developing tolerance (Deyo et al., 2015; Dueñas et al., 2016; Ray et al., 2016). Taking high levels of opioids may lead to overdose as the patient takes more and more, becoming unaware of how many opioids they are taking to address their pain (Dart et al., 2016; Deyo et al., 2015; Hayhurst & Durieux, 2016; Ray et al., 2016).

In the U.S., the rate of overdose deaths related to drugs has more than quadrupled from 16,849 in 2009 to 70,630 in 2019, of which 49,860 were associated with opioids, prescription, and non-prescription (CDC, 2021; Compton et al., 2015; National Institute of Drug Abuse [NIDA], 2021a; Ray et al., 2016). Most of the drug-related deaths occurred from illicit opioids obtained on the black market, such as heroin and fentanyl; however, initial exposure to opioids

often occurs through a prescription provided by a physician to treat pain after surgery or injury (CDC, 2021; Compton et al., 2016; Ray et al., 2016). Treatment of drug overdoses costs the U.S. government 78.5 billion dollars, including indirect costs such as family disintegration, an increased number of foster children, loss of work time, increased cost to law enforcement, and legal fees (Dieleman et al., 2016, NIDA, 2021b). Long-term opioid use does not improve pain or functioning among CP sufferers (Hoffman et al., 2017). Although California did not rank among the states with the most drug-related deaths, it did have the highest increase in drug overdose death rates. California's drug-related death rates increased from 0.9% in 2015–2016 to 4.5% in 2016–2017 (NIDA, 2020).

In 2017, opioid deaths were declared a national crisis, after which agencies and healthcare providers were tasked with developing strategies for addressing their widespread use (NIDA, 2021b). Volkow and Collins (2017) identified three strategies that could be used to address the opioid crisis, opioid reversal, addiction treatment, and pain management. These strategies could be used in any order and were supported by the literature (Chou et al., 2017; Deyo et al., 2015; Park et al., 2018 Qaseem et al., 2017; Silverstein et al., 2020).

The first strategy is opioid reversal, which involves removing a fatal opioid overdose through the administration of naloxone (Narcan; NIDA, 2018). According to NIDA (2018), several recommendations should be followed when using naloxone: (a) it should be easily accessible to patients, (b) physicians should prescribe it to their patients taking opioids, (c) law enforcement officers should be trained in its administration, and (d) it should be available over the counter.

The second strategy is addiction treatment, which involves counseling and alternatives like methadone or naltrexone (CDC, 2017). This treatment should be conducted at easily

accessible and affordable rehabilitation facilities. The third strategy is effective pain management, which requires the availability of alternatives to opioid drugs for pain management, such as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, antidepressants, anticonvulsants, cognitive therapy, self-care management, physical therapy, massage, acupuncture, music, aromatherapy, and chiropractor (Chou et al., 2017; Maher et al., 2017; Sang et al., 2018; Teichtahl et al., 2015).

To further address the opioid crisis, California began to regulate opioid prescriptions. On October 1, 2018, healthcare providers were mandated to use the Controlled Substance Utilization Review and Evaluation System (CURES 2.0) before issuing prescriptions for schedule II, III, and IV opioid medications to patients (California Office of the Attorney General, 2019). The CURES 2.0 is California's electronic prescription drug monitoring program used by clinicians and dispensing pharmacies to access patients' information on prescriptions for schedule II, III, and IV medications (California Office of the Attorney General, 2019). Class II, III, and IV scheduled medications are drugs with the potential for abuse and can lead to dependence (United States Drug Enforcement Administration [DEA]). Schedule II medications have the highest potential for abuse, whereas schedule IV medications have the lowest potential (DEA, n.d.).

The CDC guidelines for CP treatment focus on the safe initiation and maintenance of opioids (CDC, 2016). The guidelines indicate that physicians should encourage patients to use non-pharmacological therapy for pain relief and discuss treatment goals, risks, and benefits if opioids are selected for treatment (Shah et al., 2017). When prescribing opioids for the first time, the lowest dose of a short-acting medication that offers pain relief should be considered (Shah et al., 2017). These guidelines also include considering doses up to or less than 50 morphine milligram equivalents (MME/day), avoiding opioid doses that exceed 90MME/day, following up with the patient in one to four weeks after the initial dose, assessing for drug misuse through

random drug testing of urine, and referring to drug rehabilitation services for patients identified with substance use disorders (CDC, 2018; Liang & Turner, 2015; Shah et al., 2017). Substance use disorder, also referred to as addiction, occurs when a person continues to seek and use substances, despite lack of medical benefit (NIDA, 2018). This use alters mental functioning despite their negative consequences, such as loss of work or relationships (NIDA, 2018).

As a result of the federal government's attempts to address opioid use among CP sufferers, prescription opioid-related deaths decreased from 17,029 in 2017 to 14,975 in 2018, indicating a 13.5% decrease (CDC, 2020; Cicero et al., 2017; NIDA, 2020). In 2018, the rate of opioid prescriptions declined from 81.3% in 2012 to 51.4% (CDC, 2020). This has demonstrated that the CDC guidelines were effective in decreasing prescriptions for opioids; however, there is still much work to be done to address CP (Alford et al., 2016; Bohnert et al., 2018; Henry et al., 2018). Despite this decrease, the number of deaths due to non-prescription opioids, such as heroin, continues to be high (CDC, 2016; Cicero et al., 2016).

Problem Statement

In response to government recommendations to reduce opioid use, clinicians in the healthcare system have decreased the number of opioids prescribed for treating CLBP, leaving patients under-treated and with decreasing patient satisfaction (Alford, 2016; Chou et al., 2017; Deyo et al., 2015; Glowacki, 2015; Henry et al., 2018; Sinha et al., 2019). Clinicians have begun to provide patients with treatment plans that combine fewer opioids with anti-inflammatory, antidepressants, or multi-modal medications (Chou et al., 2017; Enthoven et al., 2017; Maher et al., 2017; Matthias et al., 2017; Oliveira et al., 2018; Qaseem et al., 2017).

The patients whose adjusted treatment plans are not effective do not receive alternative non-pharmacological options (Alford, 2016; Henry et al., 2018; Sinha et al., 2019). The patients

must live with their pain or search for other providers who are willing to prescribe patients' preferred medications (Henry et al., 2018; Sinha et al., 2019; Sullivan et al., 2017). This has caused anger among patients (Henry et al., 2018; Matthias et al., 2017; Sinha et al., 2019). Additionally, the changes in opioid refill practices have increased the risk of non-compliance or discontinuation of care among CP sufferers and of patients turning to street drugs to relieve their pain (Cicero et al., 2018; Cicero et al., 2017). Similarly, these changes have impacted CLBP sufferers since they often take opioid medications to treat their pain (Hanna et al., 2019; Henry et al., 2018; Sinha et al., 2019; Taichtahl et al., 2015). Research has found that low back pain sufferers became more inactive due to their uncontrolled, under-treated pain, which consequently decreased their income as they were unable to work (Hanna et al., 2019; Maher et al., 2017; Park et al., 2018, Sinha et al., 2019; Taichtahl et al., 2015).

The efficacy of opioids in treating CP has been difficult to study since many patients often drop out before follow-up due to lack of effectiveness of the treatment or intolerable side effects from the medications being used in the studies (Abdel et al., 2016). However, patients with CP who had inadequate pain relief were found to suffer from physical, emotional, psychological, and financial losses in addition to social disturbances (Carpenter et al., 2019; Maher et al., 2017; Park et al., 2018; Park et al., 2019; Sinha et al., 2019). Those patients are at risk for increased incidences of depression and anxiety, while socially, they are at an increased risk of relationship problems, sexual dysfunction, overuse of NSAIDs leading to stomach ulcers, and illicit drug use (Birke et al., 2019; Boone & Kim, 2019; Ethnoven et al., 2017; Marshall et al., 2017; Stubbs et al., 2016). Furthermore, there is an increased risk of physical disability due to decreased levels of activity, which may lead to obesity (Carpenter et al., 2019; Maher et al., 2017; Park et al., 2018; Sinha et al., 2019).

In compliance with State of California guidelines, a community-based urgent care clinic located in the city of San Bernardino in San Bernardino County, where this quality improvement (QI) project was implemented, has decreased the number of opioid prescriptions since October 2, 2018 (California Office of the Attorney General, 2019).

According to the current clinic policy created in 2012, treating low back pain should include assessment, diagnosis, and referral to an emergency room for a life-threatening diagnosis like cauda equina syndrome, meaning compression of the nerves at the lower spine (Bednar, 2016). Management of cauda equina requires emergent identification and hospitalization to prevent irreversible damage to the nerves (Bednar, 2016). The protocol also recommends supportive management of rest and the topical application of ice to the affected area. In acute injuries, it is recommended to consider pharmacological interventions for moderate-to-severe pain, including non-opioid analgesics, anti-inflammatory medications, opioids, and/or muscle relaxants (Qaseem et al., 2017; Will et al., 2018). These pharmacological interventions may be given in any order at the medical practitioner's discretion. If an opioid medication is selected, the dose should be one to two tablets every four hours for a maximum of 12 tablets in 24 hours, with a total range of 20 to 50 pills. If patients do not get adequate pain relief, they will be referred to pain management.

Federal and state opioid-related regulations require that providers review patient records from CURES before prescribing opioids (California Department of Public Health [CDPH], 2016). To comply with this regulation, the clinic recommended that returning patients who previously received prescriptions at the clinic for Class II-IV scheduled medications now receive less medication (CDPH, 2016). For example, patients who were previously receiving 90 pills of Norco, which is a class III scheduled medication, per month would be decreased to 60 pills, and

patients receiving 60 pills per month would be decreased to 30 pills. In addition to decreasing their pill count, those patients were given anti-inflammatory medications, anticonvulsants, muscle relaxants, and local anesthetics (Castro et al., 2017; Chou et al., 2017; Deyo et al., 2015; Maher et al., 2017).

Based on the current clinic policy, if these interventions did not work for patients who continued to experience pain, the patients were referred to an outside facility for pain management or physical therapy for treatment. Patients referred to pain management go to an outside medical specialty that offers services related to pain management through pharmacological interventions such as lidocaine injections, epidural injections, and higher prescribed doses of opioids (Arrowhead Orthopedics, 2018). Patients who received higher doses of opioids were not to return to the clinic; they remained with pain management. The non-pharmacological interventions (NPIs) at the pain management facility included physical therapy, counseling, and occupational therapy (Cherkin et al., 2017; Chou et al., 2017; Maher et al., 2017). Turner et al. (2018) found that providing self-care physical therapy education through community involvement improved CP and physical and cognitive functioning among patients from low socioeconomic status communities.

Should some patients return to the clinic for their usual prescription of opioids because the outside services were not able to alleviate their pain, they will be prescribed the same amount of opioids they received prior to their referral elsewhere. Currently, primary care patients transferring from another provider and receiving opioid prescriptions need to wait until the new healthcare provider receives their medical records to obtain a refill, which ensures continuity of care. As for new urgent care patients requesting opioid prescriptions, they will not be given a

prescription. They will be offered non-opioid alternatives and will be educated on obtaining opioid prescriptions from their primary care physician.

Examining the clinic protocol for managing CP, only rest and topical use of ice was recommended. Patients were not educated on non-pharmacological self-care interventions, which have been found to control CP (Hamlin et al., 2017; Harman et al., 2014; Turner et al., 2018; Wall, 2014; Wendt et al., 2019). Thus, this QI project seeks to assist the clinic's patients by providing alternative NPIs to treat their pain. Recommending alternative treatments and educating patients about them demonstrates a caring attitude by the healthcare provider, which enhances patient-provider communication and trust (Danielson et al., 2019; Henry et al., 2016; Henry et al., 2017).

Another concerning issue at the clinic was the method of measuring opioid medications. At the clinic, every opioid medication was measured by the number of pills; however, per the CDC (2016) guidelines, the number of pills should be converted to MME, which is a standard numerical measure used to determine how much morphine there is in an opioid medication; the higher the amount of MME taken per day, the higher the risk for dependence and overdose death (CDC, 2016; Deyo et al., 2015; Ray et al., 2016). Four 10 mg tablets of Norco, for instance, are equivalent to 40 MME based on the conversion factor of 1 per 1 mg of Norco, while four 50 mg tablets of tramadol, schedule IV are equivalent to 20 MME based on the conversion factor of 0.1 per mg of tramadol (Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services, n.d.).

Although the focus of the opioid crisis is on reducing and discontinuing opioid prescriptions, the recommendations allow for providers' discretion when deciding on the number of opioids to be prescribed (CDC, 2016). These changes rendered patients confused and angry, despite educating them that the changes had to occur in response to government regulations

(Henry et al., 2018; Sinha et al., 2019). Similarly, the clinic's patients often expressed anger and dissatisfaction with the new practices. Generally, patients complained that the number of pills prescribed was insufficient or ineffective in controlling their pain. In addition to opioid medications, patients received prescriptions for non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medications (NSAIDs), lidocaine patches, antidepressants, anticonvulsants, and muscle relaxants (Chou et al., 2017; Deyo et al., 2015; Maher et al., 2016). No non-pharmacological alternatives were offered to these patients when their current regime was not alleviating their pain. Hence, this QI project addressed this problem with an emphasis on offering and evaluating effective evidence-based alternatives to treat CLBP without opioids. Interventions that would help patients reduce their opioid use while providing adequate pain management and self-care for CLBP were proposed and evaluated.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this QI project was to design, implement, and evaluate a patient education program that used non-pharmacological interventions (NPIs) for treating CP in patients with CLBP at an urgent care clinic in San Bernardino County. The aim of the project was to assess changes in knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs related to NPIs among CLBP patients after completion of an educational intervention.

Supporting Framework

A theoretical framework structures a project, identifies interrelationships among factors, and guides interpretation of the findings (Imenda, 2014). Imenda (2014) compared a theoretical framework to a blueprint used to build a project and interpret the results. Thus, a theoretical framework was employed to plan, implement, determine outcomes, and interpret findings

(Imenda, 2014). Pender's Health Promotion Model (HPM) will be discussed in the following section as the model selected to guide the project.

The Health Promotion Model

The HPM was introduced by Dr. Nola Pender in 1982, revised in 1996, and 2006 (Murdaugh et al., 2019; Pender, 2011; Pender et al., 2015). The model was developed to help nurses understand the role of behavior, environment, and health outcomes in helping patients develop behaviors that promote health (Pender, 2011). It includes the components of individual, environment, nursing, health, and illnesses, as individuals are influenced by personal and environmental characteristics that can promote health (Murdaugh et al., 2019; Pender, 2011; Pender et al., 2015). Health, in the model, is defined as a state in which an individual is able to engage in healthy behaviors; whereas illness is defined as a state that interferes with an individual's ability to adhere to healthy behaviors (Murdaugh et al., 2019; Pender, 2011; Pender et al., 2015).

Concepts of the Health Promotion Model

The HPM (See Figure 1) focuses on three major components that have a linear relationship with each other; individual characteristics, behavior-specific cognitions and affect, and health-promoting behaviors (Murdaugh et al., 2019; Pender, 2011; Pender et al., 2015).

Figure 1*Health Promotion Framework*

Note. (Pender, 2011)

These three components interact to cause a behavior change, which will help to improve the health of the individual. They can be influenced externally by a nurse who can assist the patients in changing their behavior (Murdaugh et al., 2019; Pender, 2011; Pender et al., 2015).

Individual characteristics are influenced by prior related behaviors and personal factors (Murdaugh et al., 2019). Prior related behaviors are behaviors associated with events in a

person's life that can have a positive or negative influence on behavior. If an experience is perceived to be positive, then the individual is more likely to repeat the behavior that created that experience (Murdaugh et al., 2019). If an experience is perceived to be negative, the individual is likely to avoid that situation that created it (Murdaugh et al., 2019).

The personal factors are biological, psychological, and social cultural. These factors interact to influence behavior (Murdaugh et al., 2019). The biological components are the internal genetic traits that make up a person. The psychological components are the social and emotional factors that drive behaviors (Murdaugh et al., 2019). Social cultural is the environment in which the person has grown up and where they have learned to engage socially (Murdaugh et al., 2019). The biological and psychological components interact to influence the behavior a person engages in when they encounter a social cultural situation (Murdaugh et al., 2019).

The second component of the HPM is behavior-specific cognitions and affect (Murdaugh et al., 2019). This concept refers to the mind and emotional attributes that are influenced by perceived benefits or barriers of actions, activity-related affect, interpersonal influences, situational influences, commitment to a plan of action, immediate competing demands, and preferences (Murdaugh et al., 2019). If individuals think of an action as beneficial, they will be more likely to engage in it (Murdaugh et al., 2019). On the other hand, individuals may not engage in health-promoting behaviors if they perceive barriers to or difficulty with engaging in them. Activity-related affect refers to how well an individual enjoys the healthy behavior (Murdaugh et al., 2019).

Health-promoting behaviors are also motivated by interpersonal and situational influences (Murdaugh et al., 2019). Interpersonal influences come from connections with other people; such as friends, family, or healthcare providers. These interpersonal relationships consist

of norms, support, and role models. Norms determine the behavioral expectations of an individual. A person may change their behavior based on group norms. A social support system helps a person either maintain or change a behavior that can improve or be detrimental to their health. Individuals who have good or poor role models are likely to imitate their behaviors regardless of the consequences (Murdaugh et al., 2019).

Situational influences are derived from the environment and include options, demand characteristics, and aesthetics (Murdaugh et al., 2019). An individual who comes from an environment that contained many options or opportunities to engage in health-promoting behaviors will be more likely to have behavior that does not cause them harm (Murdaugh et al., 2019). Demand characteristics are the rules within the environment that require an individual to behave in a specific manner. Aesthetics are the attributes in the environments that either promote or hinder an individual's engagement in a behavior. Situational influences are external factors that determine the commitment to behavior change (Murdaugh et al., 2019).

The third component in the HPM is the behavioral outcome. A behavioral outcome is achieved when an individual creates an action plan and engages in the modified behavior (Murdaugh et al., 2019). The HPM does consider that some individuals may experience unforeseen circumstances which may interfere with health-promoting behaviors. The HPM identifies that individuals should be supported while they are attempting to change behavior. Behavior is influenced by immediate competing demands that conflict with the individual's desires. These competing demands can come from family or work obligations which may interfere with an individual's desire to stay fit or eat well. An individual who is conflicted between competing demands will have difficulty meeting or completing an action plan. An action plan is a set of goals that an individual establishes for themselves when attempting to

create behavior change. The action plan is the guiding tool that will help the individual to overcome the competing demands by outlining all possible barriers and opportunities to help the individual succeed. If an individual is able to follow the action plan, then the outcome will be engagement in health-promoting behaviors (Murdaugh et al., 2019).

The HPM Assumptions

Assumptions in theoretical frameworks provide the hypotheses used to determine if a project outcome aligns with the concepts being evaluated (Archibald et al., 2016). Pender's HPM is based on seven assumptions derived from both nursing and behavioral sciences (Murdaugh et al., 2019). These assumptions include that individuals want a lifestyle that will allow them to live healthy lives, are capable of self-evaluation and of determining when they need to change their behaviors, seek balance in their lives, monitor their behavior to maintain that balance, and have an internal biology that will cause behavior changes based on continually changing environmental triggers. In addition, healthcare professionals are integral parts of the lives of individuals and influence their health outcomes. Lastly, the individuals are self-directed in determining how they interact with their environment, which is vital to behavior change (Murdaugh et al., 2019).

Integration of the Health Promotion Model in Research

The HPM postulates that health promotion behavior is influenced by personal factors, interpersonal influences, and situational influences (Murdaugh et al., 2019). It was used in many studies to promote healthy behaviors (Armbrust et al., 2015; Ayres & Pontes, 2018; Mohsenipoua et al., 2016; Penwell-Haines et al., 2017). Armbrust et al. (2015) used Pender's HPM to encourage physical activity among patients with juvenile rheumatic arthritis, a condition characterized by CP and fatigue (Armbrust et al., 2015). To achieve this goal, the researchers

designed an internet-based and in-person program that provided theoretical education on rheumatoid arthritis and physical activities. Out of 64 participants, 93% showed commitment to the program and completed weekly requirements of one hour of physical activity and assignments. Additionally, 80% of the participants indicated satisfaction with the program (Armbrust et al., 2015). According to Pender's HPM (Murdaugh et al., 2019), commitment to a plan of action leads to health-promoting behavior. Therefore, it is imperative to design tailored educational materials for CLBP sufferers that may enhance satisfaction and increase commitment to an action plan.

The HPM was also used in research to assess health-promoting behaviors and CP control (Matthie & Jenerette, 2017; Zhang et al., 2017). In a qualitative study, the HPM guided the assessment of self-care among young African American women aged 19 to 39 with Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) who suffered from CP (Matthie & Jenerette, 2017). Two themes emerged among participants. The first theme pertained to the participants' inability to describe their pain, and the second was that participants identified themselves as CP sufferers. Participants indicated that being in pain was a common experience, and they had learned to live with it. Some of the participants stated that they perceived their pain as a burden on their family, so they often chose not to discuss it. Pharmacological and NPIs were reported to assist in coping with pain. The pharmacological interventions were pain medications and SCD medications. Some of the NPIs used were hydration, massage, prayer, yoga, exercises, and distractions like visiting with friends. The NPIs were frequently used for self-care by the participants who reported experiencing two to seven pain crises in a year. Participants who experienced more than two to seven pain crises a year were more likely to use fewer NPIs for self-care. It was suggested that nurses encourage self-care through other non-pharmacological measures, such as maintaining adequate hydration.

The inability of participants to describe their pain was an indication of the difficulties associated with SCD pain descriptors; dull, aching, or sharp. The participants felt that the descriptors provided were not accurate for their type of pain (Matthie & Jenerette, 2017). As hypothesized in the HPM, competing demands can discourage health-promoting behaviors (Murdaugh et al., 2019). Matthie and Jenerette (2017) noted the competing demands of personal responsibilities to family and life overrode self-care. Although the results of this study were significant for female patients with CP associated with SCD, it is still important to understand the impact of competing demands on CLBP.

Furthermore, the HPM was used to study variables that may influence health-promoting behaviors. Ayres and Pontes (2018) conducted a correlational study in which they applied the HPM concepts to examine how resilience (personal factor), social support (interpersonal influence), and neighborhood perceptions (situational influence) affected health promotion behaviors. The study recruited 122 adolescents, aged 13 to 18 years, living in an urban area in New Jersey. In this study, resilience was defined as the ability to deal with a stressful situation. Health-promoting behaviors like physical activity, nutrition, and spiritual health led to healthy lifestyles. Situational influences entailed the orderliness or disorderliness of the neighborhood, while social support entailed the adequacy of support participants believed they received from family, significant others, or friends. The results showed that adolescents' perceptions of unsafe neighborhoods (aesthetics) discouraged them from engaging in physical activities outdoors. This finding aligns with the HPM since the environment supports the promotion of health-promoting behaviors. Thus, in a safe neighborhood, participants were more likely to be outside engaging in physical activities. However, resilience (psychological influence) and social support were found not to affect health-promoting behaviors as hypothesized. Social support did not increase health-

promoting behaviors among adolescents since the neighborhood was perceived to be unsafe. Physical safety overrode the desire to engage in health-promoting behaviors. The HPM is useful in identifying the factors that influence health-promoting behaviors and developing strategies that may help to mitigate competing demands and promoting healthy behaviors.

Application of the Health Promotion Model

This QI project employed Pender's HPM to increase the use of non-opioid alternative treatments among CLBP sufferers, thus reducing opioid use. There are multiple shared concepts between this QI project and the HPM. Previous experiences of CP may cause fear of recurrent pain with the abandonment of opioids (prior related behavior; Carpenter et al., 2019; Darnall & Colloca, 2018; Matthias et al., 2017). Likewise, starting non-opioid treatments may cause distress due to fear of uncontrolled pain, which can be activity-related affect (Darnall & Colloca, 2018; Darnall et al., 2018; Matthias et al., 2017). According to the CDC (2018), initial exposure to opioids often occurs legally through a prescription from a provider or illegally through shared medications with family or friends. There is a relationship between CP and increased opioid use (Darnall & Colloca, 2018; Matthie & Jenerette, 2017; Matthias et al., 2017; Volkow & Collins, 2017). Therefore, to obtain effective pain relief for patients whose opioid medications have been reduced, it is vital to have a holistic perspective with NPIs tailored to them by considering the concepts proposed by the HPM that may influence patients' commitment to a plan of action as well as their health-promoting behaviors. In this QI project, the expected health-promoting behavior is using non-opioid alternative treatments to alleviate CLBP and to reduce the use of opioids.

The variables related to the HPM examined in this project were patients' characteristics, previous knowledge about non-opioid alternative treatments, functionality level, and attitudes

and beliefs about management of CP that can serve as benefits or barriers. These variables were selected because they can influence the health-promoting behavior of using non-opioid alternative treatments (Murdaugh et al., 2019). Patients' characteristics included the following demographics: age, gender, ethnicity, level of education, marital status, living status, whether or not they live alone, and employment status. Patients were asked about transportation availability and type as a situational influence. The ability to use new non-opioid alternatives to control CP and reduce opioid use was the outcome or the health-promoting behavior of this project (Murdaugh et al., 2019).

Despite the benefits of some non-opioid alternative treatments, research identified several barriers to changing behaviors related to pain management (Armbrust et al., 2015; Darnall & Colloca, 2018; Hadi et al., 2017; Matthie & Jenerette, 2017; Matthias et al., 2017). Some of these barriers were providers' lack of empathy, lack of specialized knowledge for pain management, and lack of communication with the patient. System barriers related to the wait time to see a specialist, the short amount of time spent with a primary care provider, and the lack of a multidisciplinary approach were also impediments (Hadi et al., 2017). Additionally, patients' barriers to non-pharmacological pain interventions related to cost, transportation, and lack of motivation were obstacles (Becker et al., 2017). Research indicated that increasing patients' knowledge about the benefits and risks of NPIs increased acceptability of use (Becker et al., 2017).

Nurses can bridge the gap between patients' fears and confidence in non-opioid treatments (Hadi et al., 2017; Murdaugh et al., 2019). The gap can be closed by increasing patient knowledge regarding alternative treatment options for pain management and providing information about community resources and referrals. These options provide significant support

to patients as they attempt to take control of their health (Hadi et al., 2017). Figure 2 highlights the concepts of the HPM that were used in this QI project to achieve the health-promoting behavior of using non-opioid alternative treatments for CLBP.

The HPM was a good fit (see Figure 2) for this QI project because it guided changing health behaviors of CLBP sufferers by promoting non-pharmacological alternatives. By employing the concepts of the HPM, this project assisted the San Bernardino clinic patients in using fewer opioids, reducing pain, and improving physical functioning. The HPM also helped to understand the factors that served as benefits or barriers to engage in healthy activities related to controlling CP. Finally, this model was a good fit because of its predictive value as it predicted and evaluated the variables and relationships between those variables that influenced the outcome or the health-promoting behaviors.

Figure 2

Health Promotion Model Application in Chronic Low Back Pain

Note. (Pender, 2011)

Review of Literature

The purpose of the literature review was to provide an overview of the current research regarding the topic of interest as it relates to a theoretical framework, participants, interventions, and outcomes, which can then be compared to similar studies (Baker, 2016). The literature review for this QI project focused on current research related to CLBP, its pathophysiology, and its effects on patients. The review also included patient factors that influenced the education and management of CLBP that used evidence-based interventions to treat it. The information obtained from the literature review guided the interventions implemented by this QI project at the clinic in San Bernardino County (Baker, 2016).

The literature review consisted of a search of databases that included PubMed, Google Scholar, and the Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature. The search terms were “chronic low back pain,” “non-specific chronic low back pain,” “pathophysiology,” “pharmacological interventions,” “opioids,” “non-opioids,” “non-pharmacological interventions,” “patient knowledge, beliefs and attitudes regarding non-pharmacological interventions” “chronic low back pain education” and “patient education on non-pharmacological intervention,” “teaching,” and “motivational interviewing.”

The review of the literature included 69 studies, 23 of which discussed the pathophysiology of CLBP and 46 focused on pharmacological and NPIs for the management of CLBP. Of the 46 studies, 28 were quantitative, four were qualitative (Darlow et al., 2016; Salvo et al., 2015; Rod et al., 2016; Turner et al., 2018), three were mixed-methods (Becker et al., 2018; Mehl-Madrona et al., 207; Sullivan et al., 2017), seven were systematic reviews (Bradt et al., 2016; Chou et al., 2017; Chou et al., 2018a; Du et al., 2017; Ethvonen et al., 2017; Furlan et al., 2015; Lakhan et al., 2016), and four were meta-analyses (Abdel Shaheed et al., 2016; Enke et

al., 2018; Pérez-Aranda et al., 2019; Traeger et al., 2015). The quantitative studies were 16 RCTs (Ehrouz et al., 2017; Castro & Dent, 2017; Cherkin et al., 2016; De Paolis et al., 2019; Freiwald et al., 2018; Gilbert et al., 2018; Kett & Sighting, 2019; Krebs et al., 2018; Lakhan et al., 2016; Matheve et al., 2020; Michalsen et al., 2016; Morone et al., 2016; Nasiri et al., 2016; Pando-Naude et al., 2019; Sullivan et al., 2017; Thomas et al., 2016), four quasi-experimental (Claus et al., 2017; Darnall et al., 2018; Higgins et al., 2018; Wendt et al., 2019), two prospective longitudinal (Al Yousef et al., 2018; Turner et al., 2016), and six cross-sectional studies (Benyapa et al., 2018; Herman et al., 2018; Lozier et al., 2018; Marshall et al., 2018; Park et al., 2019; Park et al., 2018).

Pathophysiology of Chronic Low Back Pain

Low back pain is felt in the region between the lower ribs and the upper gluteal muscles, which is also called the lumbosacral region (NINDS, 2020). Five vertebral bones in the lumbar spine (L1 to L5) and the sacrum make up the lumbosacral region (Urits et al., 2019). The pathophysiology of CLBP involves the structures within the lumbosacral region as well as the peripheral and central nervous system (Hartvigsen et al., 2018; Urits et al., 2019).

Unlike acute pain, which is a protective physiologic response that alerts individuals to possible tissue damage, CP may continue to manifest long after the tissue has healed (Aronoff, 2016; Crofford, 2015). Chronic low back pain is described in two ways, identifiable pathology or unidentifiable pathology (Bardin et al., 2017; Deyo et al., 2017; Stump et al., 2016). Unidentifiable etiology accounts for more than 90% of all CLBP cases (Bardin et al., 2017; Herndon et al., 2015; Maher et al., 2016; NINDS, 2020). Low back pain with identifiable pathology accounts for less than 15% of all cases (Sanzarello et al., 2016).

Identifiable Pathology

Identifiable pathology of CLBP can be described as nociceptive, based on its source (Urits et al., 2019). Nociceptive CLBP can be localized, radicular, or referred, depending on the location of the pain (NINDS, 2020; Stump et al., 2016; Urits et al., 2019). Localized pain originates from the axial lumbosacral region and may result from inflammation of the joints (Urits et al., 2019). As shown in Figure 3, radicular pain is caused by irritation of the nerve path that runs along the back of the leg from the lower back, commonly known as sciatica (Urits et al., 2019).

Figure 3

Image of the Sciatic Nerve

Note. (Orthopedic Specialists of Oakland County, 2016)

Radicular pain can be accompanied by neuropathic symptoms and involves compression of the nerve that causes numbness or weakness of the limbs (Allegrì et al., 2016; Urits et al., 2019). Referred pain occurs away from the source and does not follow a nerve path, such as muscle tension in the hips (Allegrì et al., 2016; Stump et al., 2016; Urits et al., 2019). Localized, radicular, or referred pain can coexist (Allegrì et al., 2016; Stump et al., 2016; Urits et al., 2019).

Non-Identifiable Chronic Low Back Pain

Pain that persists and has no identifiable cause may be the result of central sensitization (Allegri et al., 2016; Hartvigsen et al., 2018; Nijs et al., 2015; Urits et al., 2019). Central sensitization is another route through which pain can be processed from the central nervous system (Aronoff, 2016; Crofford, 2015; Hartvigsen et al., 2018; Sanzarello et al., 2016). There are two forms of central sensitization: secondary hyperalgesia and allodynia (Sanzarello et al., 2016; Urits et al., 2019). Secondary hyperalgesia occurs when pain is experienced in the periphery of the body but is an over-reaction to minimal stimuli (Aronoff, 2016; Crofford, 2015; Sanzarello et al., 2016). Thus, pain results from the hypersensitivity of the neurons between the brain and the spinal cord (Aronoff, 2016; Crofford, 2015; Sanzarello et al., 2016). This type of pain can also be caused by opioid-induced hyperalgesia, which is a state of heightened sensitivity to pain among patients who are on long-term opioid therapy (Sanzarello et al., 2016; Yi & Pryzbylkowski, 2015).

The second form of central sensitization is allodynia, which occurs when a non-painful stimulus, such as a simple touch, is interpreted as painful (Aronoff, 2016; Crofford, 2015; Sanzarello et al., 2016). Allodynia occurs when the spinal cord and the brain activate to maintain pain through the receptor neurons and chemical modulators that become hyperactive and hyperexcitable (Anwar, 2016; Greenwald & Shafritz, 2018; Sanzarello et al., 2016). Pain is maintained even after the non-painful stimuli are removed (Anwar, 2016; Greenwald & Shafritz, 2018). In this type, pain is maintained as a painful memory, which becomes a conditioned response to similar situations. This pain memory produces CP (Crofford, 2015; Greenwald & Shafritz, 2018). In the spinal cord and the brain, pain can be distributed to a wider region beyond the focused area of painful stimuli (Crofford, 2015; Greenwald & Shafritz, 2018;

Sanzarello et al., 2016). In such instances, CP can present as a complex regional syndrome, as seen in referred pain that is non-specific low back pain or fibromyalgia (Crofford, 2015; Greenwald & Shafritz, 2018; Sanzarello et al., 2016).

The regions in the brain that maintain CP and regional pain syndromes are also the same parts of the brain that regulate emotions and cognition (Crofford, 2015; Greenwald & Shafritz, 2018). Therefore, CP may coexist with other psychological conditions like depression, anxiety, or insomnia (Crofford, 2015; Greenwald & Shafritz, 2018). Likewise, CLBP may be influenced by biopsychosocial factors like previous experience with low back pain, catastrophizing, self-efficacy, level of education, social-economic status, sex, and age (Hartvigsen et al., 2018; Machado et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2016). A study by Yang et al. (2016) identified the factors associated with CLBP as individuals who worked under unfavorable conditions, had difficulty balancing work and family, faced job insecurity, were female, were older, and were working 41 to 45 hours a week, or younger working more than 60 hours a week (Yang et al., 2016).

Chronic Pain Management

The interventions for CP management can be unimodal, multimodal, or multidisciplinary (Hartvigsen et al., 2018; IASP, 2017; Müller-Schwefe et al., 2017; Vlaeyen et al., 2018). Unimodal interventions are not paired with other forms of treatment. Multimodal interventions involve more than one treatment. Multidisciplinary interventions occur when different disciplines work together (Hartvigsen et al., 2018; IASP, 2017). The treatment of CLBP should focus on the specific cause of the pain when the cause is known (Urits et al., 2019; Vlaeyen et al., 2018). The treatment for non-identifiable CLBP does not aim to eliminate the pain but to improve it sufficiently enough to increase function and decrease disability (Krebbs et al., 2018; Maher et al., 2017; Urits et al., 2019; Vlaeyen et al., 2018). The management should include

providing education and reassurance, pharmacological and NPIs, and evaluation to assess effectiveness (Chenot et al., 2017; Ikemoto et al., 2018; Maher et al., 2017).

Most of the guidelines available from 2008 to 2017 recommended that management of CLBP include physical therapy, psychosocial interventions, NSAIDs, tramadol, acetaminophen, antidepressants, anticonvulsants, muscle relaxants, and opioids for a short-term using the lowest effective doses (ACP, 2017; Chenot et al., 2017; Kaiser Permanente, 2017; Oliveria et al., 2018). According to the American College of Physicians (ACP, 2017), a step-wise approach for treating CLBP should start with NPIs, move to non-opioid medications, and, finally, to opioid medications if there is a lack of improvement in pain relief from the previous interventions. Unimodal interventions that involved opioids should be avoided since opioids were the option of last resort in CLBP management (ACP, 2017; CDC, 2016; Ikemoto et al., 2018). The goal of treatment was to retrain the brain to redirect neuronal connections through activities that caused the brain to focus on something other than the pain (Aronoff, 2016; Crofford, 2015; Greenwald & Shafritz, 2018; Hayhurst, 2019). Retraining the brain may be achieved by using NPIs (Aronoff, 2016; Crofford, 2015; Greenwald & Shafritz, 2018; Hayhurst, 2019).

Non-Pharmacological Management

Non-pharmacological interventions are research-based interventions used to treat some medical conditions (Aronoff, 2016; Crofford, 2015). Non-invasive NPIs were recommended as the first line of treatment for non-specific CLBP (ACP, 2017; Chenot et al., 2017). A variety of NPIs can be used to treat CLBP, such as yoga, mindfulness stress reduction therapy, tai chi, exercise, psychological therapy, multidisciplinary rehabilitation, massage, and acupuncture (Chenot et al., 2017; Cherkin et al., 2016; Chou et al., 2017; De Paolis et al., 2019; Du et al., 2017; Ikemoto et al., 2018; Müller-Schwefe et al., 2017). Some NPIs (acupuncture or

chiropractic therapy) must be administered by a skilled professional, while others (imagery, deep breathing, massage, lavender oil, music, progressive muscle relaxation, laughter, meditation, distraction, and hot or cold compresses) can be self-administered (AHNA, 2017; Chou et al., 2017; De Paolis et al., 2019; Herman et al., 2018). These interventions are considered effective, convenient, and low-risk (AHNA, 2019; Cherkin et al., 2016; Du et al., 2017). A meta-analysis study of nine RCTs among 2,188 patients with CLBP evaluated the effectiveness of self-managed NPIs on pain and disability (Du et al., 2017). The study found that self-managed NPIs, such as education, aerobic exercises, progressive muscle relaxation, and imagery taught face-to-face or online were effective in relieving pain and disability in the short term, three months, and long term, one year, with no major adverse effects reported (Du et al., 2017).

Another systematic review that included nine RCTs to evaluate the benefits and harms of NPIs for back pain found that NPIs were useful for the treatment of CLBP, mostly in the short term (Chou et al., 2017). Pain intensity was more positively influenced by NPIs. The adverse effects that were associated with the NPIs were minimal and included muscle soreness and slight bleeding with acupuncture (Chou et al., 2017). The use of NPIs to treat CLBP is considered non-threatening and non-invasive (AHNA, 2019; Darnall & Colloca, 2018), and involving patients in the decision-making process to select their treatment methods increases their compliance (Ahern et al., 2019). Therefore, NPIs can effectively become part of patients' health-promoting behaviors directed at managing their pain instead of avoiding it, which may impair their functionality, or using opioids.

Factors Affecting the Use of NPIs

A number of factors affect a CLBP sufferer's use of NPIs. These factors can work as barriers or motivators (Chou et al., 2018; Herman et al., 2018; Lozier et al., 2018). Personal

characteristics and prior related experiences such as educational status, socioeconomic status, age, social support network, knowledge of NPIs and their effectiveness, knowledge about low back pain, and past treatment of CLBP were found to influence the use of NPIs (Benyapa et al., 2018; Chou et al., 2017; Chou et al., 2018; Herman et al., 2018; Lozier et al., 2018; Müller-Schwefe et al., 2017).

Personal Factors and Prior Experiences

Lozier et al. (2018) used a cross-sectional study of 517 participants with chronic musculoskeletal pain on long-term opioid (90 days) treatment from two integrated health care systems to determine the helpfulness of NPIs, along with their correlates. Patients who were young and those with a high school education were more likely to engage in clinician-directed NPIs like physical therapy, transcutaneous electrical therapy, chiropractic care, acupuncture, group pain management classes, and massage. Patients who rated higher for pain disability reported more use of NPIs (Lozier et al., 2018). Those who reported an increase in NPI use also reported an increase in helpfulness (Lozier et al., 2018). Although the study could not identify the reason the younger participants used more clinician-directed NPIs, it may be argued that older patients may have had previous experience in pain relief using NPIs; thus, their repertoire was more extensive (Lozier et al., 2018). Older patients may also be more willing to engage in self-care, rather than wait for a physician to tell them what to do (Lozier et al., 2018; Tang et al., 2019). Patients who rated higher disability related to their pain reported more use of NPIs. Those who reported an increase in their use of NPIs also reported an increase in the helpfulness of the NPIs used (Lozier et al., 2018).

Herman et al. (2018) used a mixed-methods study to assess the characteristics of patients ($n = 2024$) who visited chiropractors for CLBP in California, Oregon, New York, Florida, and

Texas. It was found that patients who chose chiropractor services were highly educated with a professional degree or bachelors' and higher (58.0%), female (58.7%), non-Hispanic White (93.2) had insurance that covered partial payments for services (72.0%), and had incomes of more than \$100,000 (27.0%). Patients who selected NPIs tended to not have prior opioid use (Herman et al., 2018). Opioid use was found to be associated with less participation in NPIs (Becker et al., 2017; Higgins et al., 2018; Lozier et al., 2018; Mehl-Madrona et al., 2016).

In support of these results, Higgins et al. (2018) conducted a quantitative cross-sectional study with 290 veterans with chronic back pain to determine the predictors of patients' willingness to participate in technology-based versus in-person CBT. The results showed that 54% of the patients who used narcotics declined to participate in a study, reporting the reason as lack of interest. It was concluded that participants who were on opioids for the treatment of their pain might be less engaged when it came to implementing other treatment options since the opioids were working (Higgins et al., 2018). Primary care providers reported opioids as one of the perceived barriers to using NPIs to treat CP. Those patients who did not trust NPIs would be effective in treating their pain (Becker et al., 2017).

It may be argued that the types of NPIs used in the studies were not appealing to the study participants. Primary care providers (PCPs) perceived some of the barriers to using NPIs were prior usage of opioids for the treatment of CP and lack of trust that NPIs would be as effective in treating their pain as their current medications (Becker et al., 2017). Thus, it is crucial to initiate the use of NPIs before opioids to treat pain. Using NPIs will allow patients to access non-invasive, non-habit-forming methods of treatment for their pain.

Knowledge, Attitudes, and Beliefs

Patients' attitudes, knowledge, and beliefs regarding NPIs, healthcare providers, and healthcare systems were reported as barriers or motivators to using NPIs (Becker et al., 2017; Chou et al., 2018). Positive attitudes were considered motivators, and negative attitudes were perceived as barriers (Chou et al., 2018). Many patients expected to be part of the decision making about their treatment (Ahern et al., 2019). Patients expressed the desire to have an explanation of the causes and prognoses of their low back pain and to have care specific to their individual needs with consistent follow-up (Chou et al., 2018). Healthcare providers' expectations can be considered motivators to care (Becker et al., 2017; Higgins et al., 2018). Barriers to care included long wait times, cost, lack of easy access to treatments, and personal factors (Becker et al., 2017; Benyapa et al., 2018; Chou et al., 2018; Higgins et al., 2018).

Relationships between providers and patients with CLBP may affect patients' attitudes towards using NPIs (Ahern et al., 2019; Becker et al., 2017; Herman et al., 2018). A cross-sectional internet survey was conducted to understand patient's experiences and needs in accessing primary care services found that about 43% of the 426 CLBP patients reported less than moderate dissatisfaction with the care they received from providers (Ahern et al., 2019). About 79% sought care for low back pain from more than two providers, while 28% sought care from four to eight providers; PCPs, physical therapists, massage therapists, and chiropractors. Patients reported dissatisfaction with their providers when they did not believe they were fully informed about treatment options and prognosis. Although patients reported unresolved pain and decreased functioning as their main reason for seeking more treatment options, almost half (43%) expressed dissatisfaction with their care (Ahern et al., 2019).

According to Herman et al.'s (2018) study, patients' positive attitudes towards providers influenced adherence to NPIs. Most of the patients reported that they would continue to use NPIs even if their insurance ended coverage. Most patients (61%) reported they would reduce the number of sessions so that they could afford to pay out of pocket, 10% reported they would change their insurance provider to ensure continuity of care, 5% said they would seek a less expensive provider, and only 9% indicated they would consider discontinuation of the services. Although this population may have been in the higher socioeconomic status (28% earned at least \$100K), their attitudes may be reflective of their ability to pay for an NPI that they perceived as beneficial, since they were able to afford them even though they were a costly expense (Herman et al., 2018).

Similarly, Becker et al. (2017) suggested the patient-provider relationship facilitated the use of NPIs. In their qualitative study, 26 patients, 14 nurses, and 12 PCPs were placed in groups of eight and asked to discuss what they perceived as facilitators or barriers to using NPIs (Becker et al., 2017). The themes that emerged were related to access, patient-provider interaction, beliefs about interventions, and social support. The barriers reported by patients were cost, transportation, and low motivation. The facilitators reported by patients included the availability of a variety of NPIs and a team-based approach between the patient and provider. The barriers reported by the medical staff included a lack of accepting NPIs among patients on opioid therapy for pain and patients' disbelief of the efficacy of the NPIs. The medical staff also reported facilitators included policies that promoted the teaching and use of NPIs among patients (Becker et al., 2017). A caring attitude from providers may influence a trusting relationship, which laid a foundation of positive beliefs about the effectiveness of NPIs.

Several studies examined predictors of using NPIs. The aforementioned study by Higgins et al. (2018) found that a higher pain level was not a predictor of participation in CBT, and only 134 of the 290 participants (46.2%) with a reported moderate pain level consented to use NPIs. On the other hand, Lozier et al. (2018) found that CP patients with higher disabilities related to their pain used NPIs more frequently than patients with less disability. There was a strong correlation between perceived helpfulness and frequency of self-directed NPIs compared to clinician-directed NPIs (Lozier et al., 2018). Patients with high levels of perceived NPI helpfulness were more likely to use them (Herman et al., 2018; Murdaugh et al., 2019).

While CP level inconsistently predicted the use of NPIs, it was suggested that the level of perceived helpfulness increased the likelihood of using NPIs and improved beliefs and attitudes towards them. Individuals with CLBP who tended to have negative beliefs about their pain also have higher disability (Alyousef et al., 2018). Alyousef et al. (2018) conducted a two-year prospective study with 442 participants and found that participants who reported high scores for negative beliefs about their prognosis of low back pain had higher levels of disability and pain intensity. Patients who reported persistent high pain intensity reported the highest negative responses, such as the belief that low back pain indicates a lifetime of suffering from pain. Such beliefs were significantly associated with catastrophizing, which increased pain perception (Darnall & Colloca, 2018). Negative patient perceptions must be considered when educating patients with CLBP about their treatment options since those perceptions may influence the potential use of NPIs.

A qualitative study of 23 patients with acute and CLBP found that physical activities were viewed as protective from further injury and helped promote complete healing over time (Darlow et al., 2016). On the other hand, other patients viewed rest as resulting in depressed

mood and loneliness. Some patients thought some physical activities, like swimming and walking, were safe for back pain (Darlow et al., 2016). The authors concluded that perceptions of pain experiences, fear, avoidance, beliefs, and self-efficacy vary among patients; therefore, they should be handled individually without labeling (Darlow et al., 2016). In addition to attitudes, patients' level of knowledge regarding NPIs for the management of CP was found to influence acceptability and adherence of their use (Benyapa et al., 2018; Becker et al., 2017; Eaton et al., 2018; Mehl-Madrona et al., 2016). Becker et al. (2017) found that PCPs perceived increasing patients' knowledge of the risks and benefits of their treatment facilitated NPI use.

Patients with CLBP who were knowledgeable of NPIs for self-management had high self-efficacy, believed interventions would work, and had a stronger social support network (Benyapa et al., 2018; Mehl-Madrona et al., 2016). In a QI project, Mehl-Madrona et al. (2016) recruited 42 veterans with chronic musculoskeletal pain on opioids to improve pain. Participants attended group medical visits twice a month, during which they received education on NPIs and participated in NPI activities such as mindfulness techniques, guided imagery, relaxation, and yoga. Although the outcomes did not show improvement in the level of functioning, 18 participants were able to reduce their opioids from 82.1 MMEs to 32.4 MMEs, eight discontinued all opioids, and the rest of the participants maintained the same opioids usage. All participants had a significant reduction in pain intensity. Participants who did not complete their sessions in the pilot program did not increase their opioid doses. When program participants were compared with those who received the usual care, it was suggested that usual care receivers demonstrated an increase in their opioid doses from 72.1 MMEs to 86.1 MMEs (Mehl-Madrona et al., 2016). This pilot program demonstrated the importance of educating patients about

treatment options and providing them with opportunities to use them; hence, participants were empowered and actively engaged to decrease the use of opioids.

Additionally, goal-setting has been found to increase adherence to NPIs (Gardner et al., 2018). Patients with CLBP whose goals for physical activity were set either by themselves or in collaboration with their physician were able to meet their goals (Gardner et al., 2018). However, there was more patient failure to meet the goal when it was set by the physician alone without the patient's input (Gardner et al., 2018). Additionally, increasing patients' knowledge of NPIs, improved their negative attitudes and beliefs about them, in addition to considering their prior related experiences, may help healthcare providers better support those patients to establish more permanent solutions to manage their CLBP.

Availability, Accessibility, and Affordability

A CLBP sufferer may choose to use an NPI based upon its availability, accessibility, and affordability (Becker et al., 2017; Chou et al., 2017; Chou et al., 2018; Darnall & Colloca, 2018; Herman et al., 2018; Higgins et al., 2018). Perceived long wait times, lack of access to services, cost, and personal factors were found to serve as barriers to using NPIs (Becker et al., 2017; Chou et al., 2018; Chou et al., 2018; Darnall & Colloca, 2018). Distance from the healthcare facility was associated with lower enrollment in CBT (Higgins et al., 2018). Patients with CP reported transportation, cost, and lack of motivation provided by their physicians, family, and friends as the top three barriers to using NPIs (Becker et al., 2017). On the other hand, facilitators included the availability of a variety of NPIs to choose from and support from providers through follow-up. From a providers' perspective, the most frequently identified barriers to using NPIs were the inability to encourage patients to use NPIs once on opioids and patients' uncertainty regarding the efficacy of the NPIs (Becker et al., 2017). Facilitators were

viewed as increased patients' knowledge on benefits and risks of NPIs and the availability of a policy emphasizing NPIs for treatment of CP (Becker et al., 2017).

Non-Pharmacological Interventions

The NPIs of imagery and distraction, massage, lavender oil, music, progressive muscle relaxation, laughter, meditation, and hot and cold compresses were part of the toolkit utilized in this project (AHNA, 2019). Additional self-care interventions of relaxation, breathing, meditation, and exercise were included in this project since CLBP sufferers can safely practice them at their own pace.

Distraction, Imagery, Virtual Reality

Distraction, imagery, and virtual reality are NPIs that involved taking attention away from pain. Techniques like playing games or squeezing a stress ball distracted the brain from pain, which then diverted neural pain pathways to create non-pain neural pathways, leading to pain relief (Matheve et al., 2020; Tack, 2019; Thomas et al., 2016). Matheve et al. (2020) conducted an RCT to assess the effects of distraction using virtual reality games with 42 participants in the control group and 42 in the intervention group. The intervention group performed exercises using virtual reality, whereas the control group performed the same exercises without virtual reality. Distraction using virtual reality games provided a greater decrease among CLBP patients who viewed their pain as an indicator of a worsening health condition (catastrophizers) compared to patients who used distraction (hip exercise) without virtual reality games (Matheve et al., 2020).

Virtual reality games using dodge balls were shown to provide a distraction from pain among patients with CLBP (Thomas et al., 2016). The patients in the intervention group (26) participated in a game that motivated them to stretch and reach over to touch a dodge ball. Each

visit, the target would be moved further to encourage more stretching. The patients in the control group (26) participated in the game, but the dodge ball was not moved further. Although the pain difference was not significant between the two groups, the patients in the intervention group reported distraction from their pain and willingness to repeat the activity, which indicated that fear related to the activity was decreased (Thomas et al., 2016). Distracting, virtual reality, and imagery can be used to refocus the brain away from their pain sensation (Matheve et al., 2020; Tack, 2019; Thomas et al., 2016).

La Touche et al. (2020) conducted an RCT using 48 patients with CLBP designed to compare motor imagery and tactile feedback as two teaching methods for performing motor control therapeutic exercises. The researchers organized three groups of 16 participants in each group to receive three different modes of intervention; motor imagery, tactile feedback, and therapeutic exercises (La Touche et al., 2020). The first group was instructed to use imagery and lift the back while lying down supine. At the same time, the patients were asked to imagine lifting the back higher than then they were actually lifting it. In the second group, patients were to do the same back exercises, but the instructor asked them to lift their back while he touched the area of the back to be lifted. In the third group (control group), the patients were given verbal instructions on how to perform therapeutic back exercises. The results showed that patients in the motor imagery group reported more mobility when compared to the tactile group and the control group. There were no differences between the control group and the tactile group for mobility (La Touche et al., 2020). Additionally, the control groups reported having more doubt (60%) about their ability to engage in the exercises than the tactile group (40%). The motor imagery (13.3%) group had the least doubt about their ability to engage participants in the exercises than

the tactile group. There were no adverse effects noted from engaging in the exercises and no dropouts.

Massage

Massage is a therapeutic technique in which muscles were rubbed and kneaded to decrease muscle tension and relieve pain (Koren & Kalichman, 2018). Massage is another intervention that has benefits in reducing pain in the short and long term (Furlan et al., 2015; Kett & Sichtung, 2019). Research on massage for the treatment of CLBP is inconsistent. Some studies claimed massage was effective for CLBP (Furlan et al., 2015) as well as for the prevention of the occurrence of back pain (Kett & Sichtung, 2019). Kett and Sichtung (2019) found massage to be effective in relieving muscle stiffness, which may cause non-identifiable chronic back pain. An RCT to evaluate the effectiveness of a roller massage to help stiff muscles among 59 office workers who engaged in prolonged sitting found it to be effective. The participants in the intervention and the control groups were instructed to sit for 4.5 hours with 10-minute interval breaks, after which the participants in the intervention group used roller massages mounted on the wall to massage their backs for eight minutes. The control group used controlled standing for eight minutes without the roller massages. The participants from both groups experienced back muscle stiffness; however, the participants in the intervention group had a significant decrease of about 23.7% of muscle stiffness compared to the participants in the control group.

A meta-analysis of 25 RCTs conducted by Furlan et al. (2015) with 3,096 participants found inconclusive results regarding the benefits of massage for low back pain. In three of the studies, massages were conducted using a mechanical device, and, in 22 of the studies, massage was provided using a massage therapist. The massage was more effective for pain relief and

improving function in the short term when it was compared to inactive controls. However, when compared to active controls like physical therapy, massage was more effective for pain in both the short term and long term but not more effective for improving function. In the study, the evidence was graded low to very low due to the risk of bias related to massage therapists, inability to blind participants, and measuring outcomes. Based on the literature review, the researchers concluded that massage might not be effective for the treatment of back pain (Furlan et al., 2015). According to the recommendations by AHNA (2017), the effectiveness of pain management was enhanced when massage was combined with other interventions such as breathing techniques.

Lavender Oil

Research showed the effectiveness of oils in aromatherapy or combination with other therapies like massage (Lakhan et al., 2016; Salvo & Cannon-Breland, 2015). Lavender oil has been used as aromatherapy or in massage for pain management due to its anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties (Nasiri et al., 2016; Salvo & Cannon-Breland, 2015). An RCT conducted among 90 participants with osteoarthritis of the knee evaluated the efficacy of lavender oil for aromatherapy and massage (Nasiri et al., 2016). The patients were divided into three groups; One group used aromatherapy and massage with lavender oil; the second group used almond oil to massage as a placebo; and the third group received no massage and functioned as a control. Patients received instructions on how to use lavender oil at home. After the intervention, the results showed significant improvements in pain among the patients who used lavender oil and massage compared to the placebo and control groups. Lavender oil, which was used in the treatment of pain among patients with osteoarthritis of the knees, a chronic inflammatory condition, may be useful for CLBP. A systematic review on 25 RCTs with 2,050 participants

found that, among other oils, lavender oil used in acupressure was effective when used for relief of CLBP (Lakhan et al., 2016).

Music

Music is an NPI that can help to decrease CP and improve functioning (Bradt et al., 2016; Pando-Naude et al., 2019). Other benefits associated with the use of music were improvement in comorbidities, such as depression and anxiety (Bradt et al., 2016; Pando-Naude et al., 2019). No current studies have investigated music for CLBP; however, music was shown to relieve pain in other chronic conditions, such as fibromyalgia (Pando-Naude et al., 2019).

Listening to self-selected music was found to decrease pain among patients with fibromyalgia compared to listening to pink noise (Pando-Naude et al., 2019). Pink noise was used for the participants in the control group. Resting-state functional magnetic resonance imaging (rs-fMRI) was used to monitor the effects of music on neuronal pain pathways in the brain. An rs-fMRI was a safe, non-invasive technique used to measure the neuronal activity in the brain during periods of rest (Turchi et al., 2018). When patients listened to the music of their choice, the rs-fMRI showed shifting from the top down in the neural pain pathways in the spine to the executive and cognitive areas of the brain, such as the medial prefrontal cortex. The brain activity was associated with pain relief, as was reported by the participants. The researchers also found that music was attributed to the sensation of relaxation, distraction, and positive emotions (Pando-Naude et al., 2019).

In another RCT, 28 patients who participated in a vocal music therapy group reported higher levels of pain relief when compared to 27 patients who received usual care (Bradt et al., 2016). The study demonstrated that listening to and singing along with the music was therapeutic to patients with CP. Although the study was conducted on participants with general CP, Pando-

Naude et al. (2019) found similar results among patients who listened to self-selected music. The researchers found that patients had a decrease in pain compared to those who listened to pink noise (Pando-Naude et al., 2019).

Progressive Muscle Relaxation

Progressive muscle relaxation (PMR) is a technique used to progressively tighten and relax muscles in the body from the feet to the face for pain relief (AHNA, 2019; De Paolis et al., 2019; Lemmon & Hampton, 2018). An RCT conducted among participants with non-cancer-related pain used PMR and interactive guided imagery to determine their effectiveness in improving severe pain (De Paolis et al., 2019). Participants who used PMR and interactive guided imagery noted significant improvement in the severity of their pain when compared to patients in the usual care group (De Paolis et al., 2019). The findings with regards to PMR appeared to be consistent in helping to relieve pain.

Laughter

Laughter and humor have been shown to decrease pain by reducing catastrophizing thoughts and anxiety (Behrouz et al., 2017; Pérez-Aranda et al., 2019). In an RCT, elderly patients were exposed to 60-minute sessions of comedy shows or jokes once a week for six weeks, and they reported a significant reduction in pain (Behrouz et al., 2017). The patients reported significant pain reduction three weeks and six weeks after the sessions were completed (Behrouz et al., 2017). The control group had no reduction in pain relief. Pérez-Aranda et al. (2019) conducted a systematic review and noted that, although laughter was not widely used for CLBP, it showed effectiveness in reducing pain tolerance and dependence.

Meditation

Mindfulness meditation, focused meditation, and movement meditation have been shown to be effective in decreasing pain. These forms of meditation were feasible and safe in the management of CLBP (Lemmon & Hampton, 2018; Michalsen et al., 2016; Morone et al., 2016; Pantuso, 2015; Zgierska et al., 2016). Researchers have associated the effectiveness of meditation with its ability to rewire the brain by preventing the formation of interpretation of threats (pain) and increasing awareness of non-threatening activities like self-breathing or using positive words of hope (AHNA, 2019; Lemmon & Hampton, 2018; Greenwald & Shafritz, 2018; Darnall & Colloca, 2018).

Participating in meditation may help reduce pain (Mehl-Madrona et al., 2016; Morone et al., 2016; Zgierska et al., 2016). Michalsen (2016) conducted an RCT among adults aged 18 to 75 with CLBP to determine the effectiveness of focused meditation provided for six weeks. The results showed there were greater reductions in pain intensity among the patients in the focused meditation group compared to the home-based exercise group (Michalsen, 2016). Morone et al. (2016) conducted an RCT among 282 older adults with CLBP and functional limitations to determine if mind-body interventions helped alleviate pain and improve function. Mindfulness meditation is a form of mind-body intervention that includes physical activities, such as walking and lying down; and then transitioning to mindfulness, breathing, and awareness of thought. The intervention participants received eight 90-minute weekly group sessions, whereas the control group received health education group sessions (Morone et al., 2016). Results showed that, after eight weeks, the intervention group had significant improvement in pain and function level when compared to the control group (Morone et al., 2016). Although the study did not measure the use of the intervention at home, participants in the intervention group may have continued with

mindfulness meditation had it been taught in the study; thus, the benefits of pain control and function would have been maintained beyond the study (AHNA, 2017; Morone et al., 2016).

In an RCT, 68 adults with CLBP benefited from focused meditation provided for six weeks (Michalsen, 2016). The results showed there were higher reductions in pain intensity among the patients in the focused meditation group compared to the home-based exercise group (Michalsen, 2016). Other studies have found mindful meditation as an acceptable treatment for pain, with patients reporting that it was easy to learn and use at home for self-care and was easy to access in a rural community (Zgierska et al., 2016; Rod, 2016). Zgierska et al. (2016) conducted a 26-week RCT among 35 patients with CLBP who were receiving 30MMEs or higher of opioids daily for three months to evaluate if mindful meditation would be feasible, acceptable, and safe. The results showed that none of the participants complained of adverse effects, had increased compliance, and the patients who were taking more than 200MMEs decreased in opioids from 28.6% to 20.0%. In the control group, there was an increase in opioids from 21.4% to 23.1%.

Hot and Cold Compresses

Although most NPIs have been extensively studied, research is limited in the area of hot and cold compresses for CLBP (Freiwald et al., 2018; Qaseem et al., 2017). Heat therapy was found to improve strength in the structures in the areas to which it is applied. This, in turn, improved functioning among patients treated with heat (Freiwald et al., 2018). In this RCT study, the researchers sought to identify the effect of heat therapy on strength and flexibility among patients with CLBP. All patients received physiotherapy training under the supervision of a professional therapist. After the training, 88 patients were randomized into the intervention group, where a heat wrap at 40°C was applied to the lower back for eight hours for two nights

(Freiwald et al., 2018). The 88 patients in the control group did not receive the heat wrap. Results showed an increase in strength and flexibility for the patients in the intervention group. In both groups, flexibility and strength were increased; however, the heat wrap group showed greater flexibility and strength, which was believed to be due to the increase in blood flow to the area (Freiwald et al., 2018). The researcher indicated that heat had an analgesic effect on pain due to the known effect of heat (Freiwald et al., 2018).

Exercises and Yoga

Exercise has been proven to help with CLBP (Chou et al., 2017; Lemmon & Hampton, 2018; Park et al., 2019; Wendt et al., 2019; Qaseem et al., 2017). There were benefits related to pain and function when patients engaged in an exercise with usual care (Marshall et al., 2017; Qaseem et al., 2017). Older women experienced significant relief from pain after participating in a rehabilitative exercise program for 30 to 50 minutes four times a week (Wendt et al., 2019). Similarly, exercises decreased pain intensity and improved function among patients with CLBP in the short term compared to no exercises (Chou et al., 2017). In a study by Wendt et al. (2019), 21 women with CLBP participated in an RCT to determine the effects of general rehabilitation and gymnastics on their perceptions of mobility and pain. Women who participated in the general rehabilitation group had lowered their pain by 62% than women in the gymnastics group (Wendt et al., 2019). The women in general rehabilitation also had improvement in disability and function (Wendt et al., 2019).

Internet Resources

Internet-based interventions were effective as instructional and monitoring tools for self-care NPI use in relieving CP and improving quality of life (Du et al., 2017; Rod, 2016; Toelle et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2019; Wall, 2014). Rod (2016) conducted an observational study in which

200 patients with limited resources were evaluated for their ability to use internet resources, such as Twitter or blogs, in the treatment of their CP. The interventions included education on how to use NPIs like mindfulness-based stress reduction, which is a form of meditation that involved relaxation through mindfulness strategies. Mindfulness is a method of relaxation used to train a person on how to focus on the present moment. Results showed that, among patients who reported severe pain, their pain was reduced from 40% to 25%, anxiety reduced from 25% to 15%, quality of life improved from 25% to 60%, and 60% of the patients reported improvement in disability when using internet-based resources. Those with moderate pain had a reduction of 45% to 40% with internet interventions (Rod, 2016). Although the study focused on CP and not low back pain, it illuminated the benefits of using internet applications in the treatment of pain. Similarly, a meta-analysis by Du et al. (2017) showed that when patient education on NPIs was provided face to face or internet, there were similar results with moderate improvement of pain and disability.

In an RCT with eight participants, researchers compared physiotherapy only with physiotherapy and other NPIs using a cellphone application to determine the effects of NPIs in relieving pain (Yang et al., 2019). The results showed effective pain relief with the group that included physiotherapy and other NPIs. In the physiotherapy-only group, pain scores remained the same throughout the four-week study.

Pharmacological Interventions

Pain for patients with CLBP had multiple etiologies related to its source, location, and psychosocial effects that may be treated through multiple pharmacological medications, such as NSAIDs, antidepressants, muscle relaxants, and opioids (Chou et al., 2017; Ethnoven et al., 2017; Koes et al., 2018; Müller-Schwefe et al., 2017; Vlaeyen et al., 2018). Treatment should be

determined based on the etiology of pain (Sanzarello et al., 2016; Urits et al., 2019). In cases where there are non-threatening identifiable causes of pain or when there are non-identifiable causes, NPIs should be considered first. Non-Pharmacological Interventions have minimal serious adverse effects of the types associated with pharmacological interventions (Chou et al., 2017; Ethnoven et al., 2017; Koes et al., 2018; Müller-Schwefe et al., 2017; Vlaeyen et al., 2018).

Non-Opioid Medications

Non-opioid pain medications (NOPMs) are a class of pharmacological products that do not contain opioids. The most frequently used NOPMs in the treatment of CLBP are NSAIDs, antidepressants, benzodiazepines, and skeletal muscle relaxants (Chou et al., 2017; Ethnoven et al., 2017; Koes et al., 2018; Krebs et al., 2017; Vlaeyen et al., 2018). Research has found small to moderate improvement in pain relief in the short term among CLBP sufferers due to NOPMs (Chou et al., 2017; Koes et al., 2018). Antidepressants relieve pain by inhibiting the serotonin and norepinephrine reuptake within the brain, which then decreases neuronal hyperactivity and results in decreased pain (Aronoff, 2016; Crofford, 2015; Reuben, 2015, Sanzarello et al., 2016). Antidepressants are used to treat CLBP when a patient has comorbidity of depression (Baron et al., 2016). The NSAIDs work by blocking the activity of the cyclooxygenase enzymes to prevent the synthesis of prostaglandins, which decreases the inflammatory responses (Calatayud & Esplugues, 2016). Antidepressants were used for the treatment of CLBP that was accompanied by inflammation (Abdel Shaheed et al., 2016).

The anticonvulsants Pregabalin, Gabapentin, and Topiramate have been used for CLBP of radicular and neuropathic etiology. The medications work by binding to the alpha and delta voltage calcium channel gates in the spinal cord, leading to a decrease in the release of

glutamate, norepinephrine, and substance P, which results in decreases pain (Sanzarello et al., 2016). However, a meta-analysis of 9 RCTs with 859 participants found that these medications were ineffective for treating pain and decreasing disability in the treatment of CLBP (Enke et al., 2018). The medication had significant side effects such as drowsiness, somnolence, and nausea (Enke et al., 2018). Acetaminophen works by enhancing the serotonergic effect, inhibiting the pain pathways descending from the brain, and decreasing excitability in the central nervous system (Sanzarello et al., 2016). Acetaminophen was used in the treatment of acute nociceptive pain caused by an injury (Sanzarello et al., 2016). Overall, acetaminophen has not shown consistency in relieving CLBP (Abdel Shaheed et al., 2016; Sanzarello et al., 2016; Qaseem et al., 2017).

Using NOPMs for pain relief has not shown significant improvement for patients in the areas of disability and function, although they have been effective in decreasing pain intensity (Krebs et al., 2018; Oldfield et al., 2019; Rasmussen et al., 2016). However, as in opioid medications, adverse effects have been reported with NOPMs (Chou et al., 2017; Koes et al., 2018; Rasmussen et al., 2016). Oral NSAIDs can cause gastrointestinal, cardiovascular, or renal complications. Muscle relaxants and benzodiazepine can cause dependency or drowsiness. Antidepressants can cause dry mouth or drowsiness (Hsu et al., 2019; Krebs et al., 2018). Other commonly used medications like acetaminophen, systemic corticosteroids, and anticonvulsants have not shown consistent effectiveness in treating CLBP (Chou et al., 2017; Koes et al., 2018; Oliveira et al., 2018).

A systematic review was conducted by Ethnoven et al. (2017) of 13 studies to determine the effectiveness of NSAIDs versus placebo for CLBP sufferers. When the medication was administered over six to 12 weeks, the researchers found a significant difference in pain relief

among patients taking the NSAIDs (Ethnoven et al., 2017). Six of the studies found adverse effects associated with NSAIDs but not significantly more than the adverse effects found in the placebo group. The researchers concluded that more than 12 weeks was needed to determine if adverse effects were evidenced by prolonged use because the studies had low statistical power (Ethnoven et al., 2017).

Topical treatments such as lidocaine patches have been effective in the treatment of CLBP (Castro& Dent, 2017; Santana et al., 2020). However, researchers have argued that the effectiveness of patches may be related to a placebo effect, in which the perception of pain relief may be related to the presence of a transdermal patch (Santana et al., 2020). The lidocaine patches have been known to cause skin irritation, dermatitis, or itching (Castro& Dent, 2017; Santana et al., 2020). Over-the-counter lidocaine was found to be as effective as prescription lidocaine in the treatment of moderate-to-severe back pain and arthritis (Castro & Dent, 2017). Overall, the research is inconsistent regarding lidocaine patches as a treatment for CLBP. The use of NOPMs should be initiated after NPIs have been attempted. Once it is determined that a pharmacological intervention is needed, then NOPMs should be the initial medications given. These medications have the advantage of providing anti-inflammatory benefits and playing a dual role in helping to address depression, which can lead to an increased level of functioning. Non-opioid pain medications are non-habit forming, so they can be used for longer periods than opioids. These NOPMs helped to decrease pain and therefore may decrease the need for stronger medications.

Opioid Medications

Opioids continue to be widely used and are the most common form of treatment for CLBP (Foster et al., 2018; Krebs et al., 2018; Reinecke et al., 2015). Opioids work by targeting

the opioid receptors that have inhibitory effects on the presynaptic and postsynaptic nerves (Sanzarelli et al., 2016). Opioids have short-term benefits for patients with CLBP when taken for less than 12 weeks (Baron et al., 2016; Gudin et al., 2020; Petzke et al., 2020). Higher doses of opioids provided more pain relief among patients with CLBP; however, this increased the chance of side effects such as headache, somnolence, constipation, dry mouth, tolerance, dependence, and death (Abdel Shaheed et al., 2016; Baron et al., 2016). A systematic review and meta-analysis of 20 RCTs with 7,925 CLBP patients were conducted to evaluate the efficacy of pain relief and disability outcomes for patients taking opioids (Abdel Shaheed et al., 2016). The patients received various doses of opioids to measure the effects on their pain. Chronic low back pain patients reported an increase in pain relief when given 40 to 240MMEs of opioids (Abdel Shaheed et al., 2016). Although the patients experienced pain relief, 50% withdrew from the studies due to adverse effects and lack of consistent pain relief (Abdel Shaheed et al., 2016). It should be noted that the patients in the studies had been previously receiving opioids through their PCPs; however, due to their participation in the studies, their opioid dosages were changed based on the groups in which they were placed.

Research was limited on the efficacy of using opioids beyond 12 to 15 weeks for providing long-term pain relief (Abdel Shaheed et al., 2016; Gudin et al., 2020; Volkow & Collins, 2017; Williams et al., 2016). Long-term use of opioids, especially when doses were high, was associated with more serious adverse effects such as opioid-induced hyperalgesia, tolerance, dependence, or death (Darnall & Colloca, 2018; Kaye et al., 2017, NIDA, 2018; Shah et al., 2017; Sullivan et al., 2017; Turner et al., 2016). Patients who took 15 to 300MMEs per day experienced higher levels of pain to the degree that it interfered with their daily activities when compared to patients taking less than 5MMEs per day (Turner et al., 2016). The findings might

be associated with the effect of opioid-induced hyperalgesia, which caused increased sensitivity to pain for patients who have been on long-term opioid therapy (Darnall & Colloca, 2018; Yi & Pryzbylowski, 2015).

Patients who took opioids for one day had a 6% probability of continuing their use for one year (Shah et al., 2017). This probability increased the more days a patient took opioids. A patient taking them for eight days or more had a 13.5% probability of using them for a year (Shah et al., 2017). Additionally, a patient taking opioids for 31 days or more had a 29.9% chance of taking them for more than a year (Shah et al., 2017). Similarly, patients who received 400MMEs to 799MMEs of opioids were two to three times more likely to become long-term opioid users compared to patients who used doses lower than 120MMEs (Shah et al., 2017). In the U.S., 26 states have enacted laws restricting opioid use for acute pain to 13 days or more, with most States only allowing no more than a seven-day supply (Davis et al., 2019).

Patients taking opioids for the long term can develop tolerance and dependence. Tolerance occurred when patients needed to keep increasing the number of pills they take to obtain the same level of pain relief (Sullivan et al., 2017; Kaye et al., 2017; NIDA, 2018). Dependence occurred when a patient continued taking substances to reverse unpleasant symptoms such as extreme hunger, fatigue, or agitation when the substances were stopped abruptly (NIDA, 2018). Patients continued taking opioids to avoid these side effects (Turner et al., 2016).

In addition to the side effects associated with opioid use, patients who took opioids for CP used more doses of opioids and non-opioid medications compared to the patients who had not initiated opioids as a form of treatment (DiMarco, 2019). There was no difference in pain related to the function between opioids and non-opioids. Additionally, non-opioids significantly

decreased pain intensity when compared to opioids in an RCT among 240 participants with CLBP and knee and hip osteoarthritis (Krebs et al., 2018). Furthermore, the participants in the opioid group reported more adverse effects than those in the non-opioid group (Krebs et al., 2018). Therefore, opioids should be avoided for treatment of CLBP, and, if considered, the lowest effective doses should be used for the treatment of moderate-to-severe pain in the short term. Typically, patients should only be given opioids after they do not obtain pain relief from treatment with NPIs and non-opioid medications.

Education on Chronic Low Back Pain and Use of Non-Pharmacological Interventions

Patient education related to the neuroscience of pain is relatively new, with its introduction occurring in the last 10 years (Louw et al., 2016). This type of education was referred to as pain neuroscience education (PNE; Louw et al., 2016). Providing patients with education about the relationship between CP and the brain (neuroscience) reduced the likelihood that patients with CLBP will catastrophize the meaning of their pain (Claus et al., 2017; Müller-Schwefe et al., 2017; Rufa et al., 2019). Education provided to patients about CP helped to change their belief systems (Rufa et al., 2019). Oftentimes, CLBP sufferers associated their pain with worsening complications (Darnall & Colloca, 2018; Puentedura & Flynn, 2016). When patients understood the role of the brain in pain perception, their worrying decreased because they understood the source of their pain was their brain rather than directly the low back (Puentedura & Flynn, 2016; Traeger et al., 2015). There was evidence that patients with CLBP, when provided education, experienced long-term reassurance that their pain will not worsen with NPIs (up to 12 months), and the NPIs can improve their pain level (Traeger et al., 2015).

A systematic review using 24 RCTs among patients with CLBP determined that education and communication on CLBP were effective in helping to increase knowledge,

providing behavior modification, and increasing compliance with physical activities (Barbari et al., 2020). Education and provider communication, in combination with other NPIs were effective in the short term (< 3 months) and the long term (6–12 months). The educative and communication strategies were combined with CBT, coaching, mindfulness, pain science education, self-care management, graded exposure, or graded activity. Multimodal interventions that combined education, CBT, and graded exposure were found to be the most effective in behavior modification and adherence to physical activities. Although pain science education was identified as a relatively newer intervention (with most of the research found in the grey literature), it was considered effective in the treatment of CLBP (Barbari et al., 2020). When patients were knowledgeable about the pathophysiology of CLBP, it changed their beliefs and attitudes towards their pain, making them more willing to try and accept NPIs as interventions for pain.

Consistent with these results, a quasi-experimental feasibility study evaluated the effects of PNE using a convenience sample of adults ages 65 and older with CLBP (Rufa et al., 2019). In this study, 25 patients were offered two one-on-one semi-structured education sessions and were instructed to read a booklet titled “Why Do I Hurt” between sessions. The booklet was designed to provide evidence-based education about the neuroscience of CP (Louw, 2013). The first session included a pretest on patients’ knowledge, and patients were then provided 60 minutes of PNE education (Rufa et al., 2019). The second session, which was scheduled two weeks after the first, lasted 30 minutes with a posttest given after the session. After the education, 24 out of 25 patients reported that they learned something new, the information was interesting and easy or very easy to read, and they would recommend the booklet to friends. Additionally, there were significant positive changes in fear of movement, disability scores, and

function. All patients were satisfied with the information, felt it helped relieve their pain, and indicated the information as believable (Rufa et al., 2018).

When patient education was combined with other forms of NPIs, such as massage or exercises, CLBP sufferers had decreased pain and disability, increased functioning and utilization of healthcare services, and improved psychosocial functioning (Claus et al., 2017; Mehl-Madrona et al., 2016; Puentedura & Flynn, 2016). However, researchers have cautioned against the use of massage for CLBP which may worsen their pain due to allodynia. Allodynia occurs when the nerves are stimulated from rubbing the muscles, which then activates the sensation of pain. The stimulation activates nerves in the area, causing the patient to feel pain when it is supposed to feel good. This type of pain is associated with central sensitization in CP (Sanzarelo et al., 2016; Urits et al., 2019).

A qualitative prospective cohort study was conducted with 129 back surgery patients to assess the effects of the use of an educational booklet called “Your Back Book” in decreasing post-surgery disability (Claus et al., 2017). The educational booklet contained information about the surgery and EBP benefits of early return to physical activities and to work. Two months after back surgery, disability did not differ between the two groups, and patients who were provided with the educational booklet reported significantly less fear-avoidance behaviors toward physical activity compared to the patients who received no educational intervention (Claus et al., 2017).

A qualitative meta-analysis of 14 trials that combined RCTs and non-RCTs with 4,872 patients found that providing patient education on the favorable prognosis of their low back pain was effective in providing long-term reassurance (Traeger et al., 2015). The education offered at the primary care visit increased the patient’s reassurance and reduced the frequency of primary care visits when compared with usual care or control education (Traeger et al., 2015). Although

the studies were conducted among patients with acute and subacute low back pain, they were relevant for the present project since unresolved acute pain may progress to CP (Crofford, 2015; Urits et al., 2019; Yi et al., 2015). Providing patients with education regarding their back pain and back surgery appeared to help alleviate their fears about movement and prognosis. The education increased the patient's knowledge about their back pain and helped to change their thinking regarding their pain.

Motivational Interviewing (MI) was an evidence-based method of communication that helped people make a change and overcome ambivalence towards the change (Gilbert et al., 2017; Mumba et al., 2018; Salvo & Cannon-Breland, 2015; Scheffel et al., 2019). The MI approach has the interviewer focus on the patient's strengths as well as their efficacy for change and provides support while the patients change their self-driven behavior (Harman et al., 2014; Higgins et al., 2018; Mumba et al., 2018). Salvo and Cannon-Breland (2015) described five key processes in the MI approach, engaging, focusing, collaborating, evocating, and planning. The engaging process was when the provider listens to the patient and then focuses on what the patient was saying without giving advice. The interviewer listened more than talked and demonstrated empathy while communicating with the patient. Collaboration occurred when the provider worked with the patient as a partner (Salvo & Cannon-Breland; 2015). Evocation involved the interviewer sharing options that were available and providing gentle suggestions for change (Salvo & Cannon-Breland, 2015). The MI process helped patients to gain confidence, when the patient was taking their first steps toward initiating change (Salvo & Cannon-Breland, 2015). The interviewer allowed patients to make their own decisions and ultimately supported the patients in carrying out their plans, regardless of the interviewer's opinion of the patients' choice.

Motivational Interviewing has been shown to improve adherence to pain management regimes (Darlow et al., 2016; Darnall et al., 2018; Holden et al., 2015). A cross-sectional study of 110 CP patients who were provided MI along with education on tapering down their opioids found a 50% reduction in opioids use (Darnall et al., 2018). When support and reassurance were provided to the CP sufferers were able to taper down 5% in the first month, then 10% per week in the following months. Monthly appointments were maintained to assess for complications. At four months, 51 participants had decreased their doses of opioids from 288 MMEs to 150MMEs. The pain level had not increased from baseline, and none of the patients experienced withdrawal symptoms (Darnall et al., 2018). Patients with CLBP may feel misunderstood by medical providers due to constant complaints of pain. Motivational interviewing improved provider-patient communication encouraged patient participation in planning and decision making, and promoted adherence and long-term use of NPIs (Darnall et al., 2019).

Analysis of Literature

Although the majority of the studies included in the literature review used large samples ($n = 5000-17,13$; Chou et al., 2017; Ethnoven et al., 2017; Furlan et al., 2015; Park et al., 2018; Park et al., 2019; Pérez-Aranda et al., 2018; Petzke et al., 2020), some of them had small numbers of participants ($n \leq 100$; Becker et al., 2017; Castro et al., 2017; Claus et al., 2017; Darlow et al., 2016; Gilbert et al., 2018; Higgins et al., 2018; Matheve et al., 2020; Mehl-Madrona et al., 2016; Michalsen et al., 2016; Morone et al., 2016; Nasiri et al., 2016; Pando-Naude et al., 2019; Rufa et al., 2019; Sullivan et al., 2017; Tack, 2019; Yang et al., 2019; Zgierska et al., 2016). Other studies used sample sizes between 100 and 500 (Higgins et al., 2018; Rod, 2019; Toelle et al., 2019; Turner et al., 2018). One feasibility study used a sample of

eight participants (Yang et al., 2019). Small samples may affect the credibility and generalizability of the results (Matheve et al., 2020; Michalsen et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2019).

The studies with participants who had similar demographic characteristics had limited generalizability as the results may not apply to different populations (Darlow et al., 2016; Higgins et al., 2018; Mehl-Madrona et al., 2016; Morone et al., 2016; Nasiri et al., 2016; Rufa et al., 2019; Zgierska et al., 2016). The large meta-analysis studies lacked heterogeneity, which limited comparisons to populations different from the samples in the studies (Petzke et al., 2020; Reinke et al., 2016; Traeger et al., 2015). A meta-analysis study reported a limitation related to potential bias associated with difficulty in determining the consistency of the intervention for how deep massage was performed (Furlan et al., 2015). Other reported limitations in cross-sectional studies were reliance on self-report information by participants for data collection and outcomes (Matheve et al., 2020; Nasiri et al., 2016; Rufa et al., 2019; Sullivan et al., 2017; Zgierska et al., 2016) and lack of causal relationships in which an independent variable was determined as the cause of change to a dependent variable (Higgins et al., 2018; Park et al., 2019; Park et al., 2018). Many of the studies reviewed reported difficulty recruiting and maintaining participants in studies involving NPIs because participants did not want their medications decreased (Higgins et al., 2018; Matheve et al., 2020; Mehl-Madrona et al., 2016; Michalsen et al., 2016).

This review of the literature discussed the benefits of NPIs and the limitations encountered by researchers. Patients with CLBP were provided information on self-directed and clinician-directed NPIs and encouraged to select based on individual preference.

Conclusion

Studies on pharmacological interventions for the treatment of CLBP demonstrated small to moderate effectiveness in relieving pain for short-term pain relief (Krebs et al., 2018; Hartvigsen et al., 2018; Maher et al., 2017; Urits et al., 2019; Vlaeyen et al., 2018). Most of the studies reviewed also revealed that pharmacological interventions had small to no effect on function and disability and all of them were associated with small, moderate, or serious adverse effects, such as drowsiness, addiction, and death (Chou et al., 2017; Deyo et al., 2016; Hartvigsen et al., 2018; Krebs et al., 2018; Maher et al., 2017; Qaseem et al., 2017; Silverstein et al., 2020; Urits et al., 2019; Vlaeyen et al., 2018).

Although some of the NPIs provided small to moderate pain relief among CLBP patients, they did not cause serious adverse effects (Chou et al., 2017; De Paolis et al., 2019; Du et al., 2017; Ikemoto et al., 2018; Müller-Schwefe et al., 2017). Non-pharmacological interventions improved function, decreased disability, promoted return to work, and improved psychological factors such as depression (Chou et al., 2017; De Paolis et al., 2019; Du et al., 2017; Ikemoto et al., 2018; Müller-Schwefe et al., 2017). These types of improvements were not associated with opioid use. This review of the literature identified multiple interventions for treating CLBP. Although different interventions had short-term effectiveness, long-term effectiveness is not clear (Chou et al., 2017; Qaseem et al., 2017). Additionally, more evidence was needed to determine specific guidelines on how to use NPIs effectively (Eaton et al., 2017; Maher et al., 2017; Qaseem et al., 2017).

An educational program to help patients understand their pain and the role of NPIs was imperative in relieving CLBP. The opioid crisis has compelled healthcare providers to respond by decreasing the number of opioid prescriptions without providing other means of pain

management (Darnall & Colloca, 2018). Chronic low back pain sufferers who received education regarding their pain used NPIs and self-tapered their opioid medication to almost half their dose without significant side effects (Darnall et al., 2018). Thus, NPIs may offer an acceptable alternative for pain relief among CLBP sufferers.

Methods

The purpose of this QI project was to design, implement, and evaluate a patient education program that uses NPIs for treating patients with CLBP at an urgent care clinic in San Bernardino County. The aims of the project were to assess changes in knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs related to NPIs among participating patients after completion of an educational intervention and develop an educational protocol that follows evidence-based practices and the CDC's (2016) updated guidelines and recommendations.

Design

This QI project used an interventional pretest/posttest design to increase the use of NPIs and decrease opioids use to relieve CLBP. The pretest-posttest design was characterized by its simplicity in administration and analysis of the results (Alessandri et al., 2017). However, the design had limitations related to instrument reactivity or placebo effects. Instrument reactivity occurs when the research instrument provides hints of the expected outcomes. The research participants may have focused on providing a desired response during the post-test assessment, given that they were administered the same assessment at the pretest. The pretest-posttest design also increased the likelihood of experiencing a placebo effect, which occurs when participants believe that the intervention should work (Alessandri et al., 2017).

Setting

This QI project was implemented at a community-based, private for-profit clinic located in the city of San Bernardino in San Bernardino County. The clinic provides both urgent care and primary care services and has two providers who prescribe medications. The primary care conditions seen in the clinic were CP, osteoarthritis, migraines, hypertension, diabetes, hypocholesteremia, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Urgent care was provided for

conditions such as respiratory infections, diarrhea, vomiting, minor injuries, and dermatitis. Healthcare providers at the clinic saw between 30 and 60 urgent care or family practice care patients daily. At least 40% were examined for uncontrolled CLBP. Therefore, many of the office visits were for opioid medication refills (Medirec, 2020).

The clinic has seven examination rooms, one treatment room, and a large waiting room. There were two healthcare providers, a family practice physician (FPP) and a family nurse practitioner who was the project author. The clinic staff included six medical assistants (MAs) and one janitor. The clinic was open seven days a week and was staffed daily with at least one medical provider and three MAs. All primary care patients were seen by one of the providers. There were 4,000 patients empaneled to the FPP.

Participants

Patients seen at the project clinic were adult men and women, older adults, and children. More than 80% of the patients have Medi-Cal and/or Medicare insurance. More than 50% of the patients seen at the clinic were African American. The remaining patient population consisted of Hispanics, Whites, and Asians. The clinic's patients were 57% female and 43% male (Medirec, 2020).

The eligibility criteria for participants in the project were men and women with CLBP who returned to the clinic for opioid prescription refills, were at least 18 years of age, had pain for three months or longer, and had received a previous prescription refill from a provider at the project clinic. Patients were excluded from the project if they did not suffer from CLBP, had cancer pain regardless of the pain location, or were non-English speakers. The project consisted of 30 patients.

Ethical Considerations

The project was submitted for approval to the Institutional Review Board (IRB) at California State University, Fullerton. Permission to conduct the project was granted by the clinic director (Appendix A). The project assumed minimal risks to participants as it involved non-invasive interventions, education, and data collection through surveys. Patients received information with no changes to their medication unless they requested it. Patients who experienced distress because of participating in the project were referred to a crisis hotline in the city of San Bernardino, but no patients required a referral.

No identifying demographic information was collected. The pre- and post-surveys were administered and numbered based on the order in which they were received. To follow up with participants and to keep them anonymous, a number was assigned to each one during pre-intervention data collection. All information was kept confidential and stored on a password-protected laptop kept in the project author's (PA) locked office.

Participation in the project was voluntary, and patients signed a consent form to participate. The PA placed the signed consent form in an envelope stored in a locked cabinet in the PA's locked office. Participants were notified that they could opt out at any time during the project without any consequences to them and that the results of the project would be reported collectively.

Procedure

Participant recruitment began immediately after obtaining IRB approval. The PA educated patients who met the eligibility criteria about the project and its purpose. The PA also addressed any concerns or questions about the project. If the patient chose to participate, they were asked to carefully read the consent form and sign it. The consent form provided a

description of the project and its purposes and discussed their rights (Appendix B). Pre-intervention data about knowledge and attitudes/beliefs were collected prior to beginning the education to obtain baseline data. The survey was administered while participants were waiting to be seen by the HCP. Participants were asked to stay an extra 20 to 30 minutes after their visit to receive the educational intervention using the educational pamphlet and the Pain Relief and Self-Care (PRSC) Toolkit.

After participants received the educational intervention, the PA contacted them twice a week via telephone to assess the number and types of NPIs used, pain level, pain interference with life activities using the PEG, and number of opioid pills taken. The data collection continued for eight weeks. Post-intervention data about knowledge and attitudes/beliefs were collected after Week 8 when the patient returned to refill their opioid prescription. During the twice-weekly calls, participants were encouraged to try at least one NPI. Figure 4 demonstrates the timeline of the project.

Figure 4

Timeline for the Project

Participants who had not practiced any NPIs or whose pain levels were not changing received an additional appointment with the PA to evaluate their needs. Three patients required an additional appointment with the PA, who referred them to pain management. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, two of the patients could not be seen at pain management, and the third patient was referred to physical therapy. These patients continued to participate in the

project, and they were encouraged to continue to try the NPIs. After analyzing the project data to obtain results, a set of recommendations related to patient education about NPIs and opioid use were developed as a protocol to be followed by all the healthcare providers at the clinic to ensure consistency and sustainability of the use of NPIs.

The Educational Intervention

Participants were educated about their pain and NPIs through an educational pamphlet and the PRSC Toolkit (Appendix C). The PA developed the educational pamphlet to include a diagram of the nervous system with the structures of the lower back that explained the pathophysiology of pain, its causes, and treatment options.

Pain Relief and Self-Care Toolkit

The AHNA (2019) offered the PRSC Toolkit. It contained information about self-care pain management. The NPIs included in the AHNA Toolkit were evidence-based self-care interventions (AHNA, 2019). This toolkit provided education about NPIs and resources that allowed participants to continue NPIs at home. This toolkit discussed relaxation, meditation, and imagery, distraction, hot and cold compresses, massage, essential oils, music, and laughter (AHNA, 2019). Additionally, downloadable free applications were included in the toolkit to provide participants access to relaxation techniques and assist them in documenting their physical activity. The education used both the pamphlet and the toolkit, which took approximately 20 to 30 minutes to complete. The patients were educated and encouraged to ask questions through MI strategies.

Data Collection

Demographics Survey

Baseline data collection prior to conducting the educational intervention took place during the initial visit, where the participants were asked to complete three surveys; each survey took five minutes or less. The first survey requested information regarding the participants' sociodemographic data, including age, gender, level of education, employment, marital status, living arrangements, and annual income (Appendix D). The Low Back Knowledge Questionnaire (LKQ) was used to collect data about knowledge related to CLBP and NPIs. Finally, the Survey of Pain Attitudes (SOPA) assessed participants' attitudes and beliefs about using NPIs. Additionally, the Pain Enjoyment of Life and General Activity (PEG) survey was administered twice a week to assess pain interference with life activity.

Low Back Pain Knowledge Questionnaire

The LKQ was developed at the Federal University of São Paulo, Brazil, in 2009, to evaluate patients' knowledge regarding low back pain (Maciel et al., 2009). The LKQ included 16 multiple-choice questions with five options for each question (Appendix E). Obtaining a higher score after conducting the intervention indicated that the patient gained knowledge about low back pain. The questionnaire was found to be valid, sensitive, and replicable with a Spearman's coefficient Interclass and intraclass validity that ranged between 0.61-0.95 (Maciel et al., 2009). The LKQ was widely used in research and clinical settings to assess knowledge of low back pain pre- and post-education (Claus et al., 2017; Rufa et al., 2019).

Survey of Pain Attitudes

The project utilized the Survey of Pain Attitudes-Brief version (SOPA-B), which was derived from the SOPA. The SOPA was first developed in 1987 by Jensen et al. (1987). It was

designed to assess the attitudes of patients with CP towards their pain. It consisted of 57 items using a 5-point Likert scale (Jensen et al., 1987). In 1997, a brief version of the SOPA was developed to decrease the number of items to efficiently use it in primary care settings (Tait & Chibnall, 1997). The SOPA-B contained 30 items and used a 5-point Likert scale, with 0 being very untrue to 4 being very true (Appendix F). A high score was an indication that the patient had a negative attitude towards their pain. The SOPA-B was considered more convenient to administer because patients spent less time responding to the questions. Permission to use SOPA-B was obtained from the publisher (Appendix G)

The brief version demonstrated strong correlations of 0.79 to 0.97 compared with similar factors in the original SOPA, which showed strong correlations (Tait & Chibnall, 1997). The SOPA-B was used internationally, across multi-ethnic populations (Duquette et al., 2005; Ferreira-Valente et al., 2019; Vanhaudenhuyse et al., 2017). In a study conducted among French participants, two surveys of the SOPA-B were administered two weeks apart and had significant correlations between all the factors indicating strong test-retest reliability, with *p*-values above 0.05. The survey demonstrated satisfactory internal consistency, with estimated values of 0.7-0.9 (Duquette et al., 2005).

A study that used the SOPA-B among patients with CP determined that higher disability and pain were correlated with negative beliefs that pain signified worsening conditions (Vanhaudenhuyse et al., 2017). Pain education and physiotherapy were associated with an increase in SOPA-B scores, indicating increased positive attitudes towards pain (Vanhaudenhuyse et al., 2017).

Pain, Enjoyment of Life and General Activity Scale

The PEG scale was a three-item survey that was developed in 2009 from a longer version of the 31-item Brief Pain Inventory (Appendix H). The PEG scale was designed to assess pain and functional status among patients with CP by measuring pain intensity and pain interference with the individual's routine activities. It entailed self-reported improvements in pain and functioning. The first item on the PEG scale required the patient to rate his/her pain (Krebs et al., 2009). The second item was a rating for how the patients' pain was interfering with their enjoyment of life. The third item was a measure of the interference of pain in the patient's general activity. A low score on this 10-point Likert instrument indicated that pain was not interfering with the patient's life in the area of enjoyment and activity.

Due to PEG's short administration, it was efficient and convenient to use. The PEG scale was valid, feasible, and sensitive to changes in the primary care setting. It had good construct validity, with a reliability of 0.73 to 0.89 (Krebs et al., 2009). The PEG scale has been used in research and clinical settings. It was used in a cross-sectional study to evaluate the relationship between pain intensity and seven quality of life indicators. The pain was related directly to general activity, mood, walking ability, working, relationships with other people, sleep, and enjoyment (Putri et al., 2020). The PEG scale was also used to compare pain and pain interference with life activity among 2,843 HIV-positive and 975 HIV-negative multi-racial and multi-ethnic women across 10 States (Sharma et al., 2018). Pain was found to interfere with general activity, mood, walking ability, working (work outside and inside of the house), relationships with other people, sleep, and enjoyment (Sharma et al., 2018).

This scale was used in clinical practice to investigate preoperative outcomes and length of stay in the hospital. Higher pain levels were associated with longer hospital stays. The PEG

scale had been used in multiple clinical setting to assess pain and its interference among patients with CP from cancer (Hale et al., 2017), in a pre- and post-operative pain study (Rojjanasrirat & Rice, 2017) and to assess outcomes after pain treatment with opioids (Larson et al., 2018).

Morphine Milliequivalent

To ensure consistency and to evaluate based on CDC guidelines, opioid prescriptions were reported in MMEs. Participants self-reported their pill count each week and at each refill visit to determine the number of opiates used at baseline, during the project, and at posttest after completion of the education intervention. An MME online calculator was used to assess opioid intake. Reduction in MMEs was used in this project as one of the indicators of pain improvement (Darnall et al., 2018; Sullivan et al., 2017).

Data Analysis and Evaluation

This project utilized QI Macros[®] and Intellectus Statistics[™] to analyze the data. The analysis tests included run charts, control charts (C-charts, I charts and X bar S chart descriptive analysis, and paired samples *t*-Tests, Table 1).

Table 1*Evaluation and Measurement of Outcomes*

Outcome	Operational Definition	Method of Measurement	Analysis
Number of NPIs	Patients were asked to identify the number of NPIs used in the past week.	Telephone call (Twice a week)	Run charts, then C chart – will be used to count the number of NPIs used per week for the population of all patients
Type of NPIs	Data were collected on the types of NPIs used	Telephone call (Twice a week)	Descriptive analysis, frequency distribution
Pain Level	Patients will be asked to identify their pain level over the past week	Telephone call (Twice a week) using Pain, Enjoyment of Life and General Activity (PEG)	Run chart then I-chart -average score across the population/ may also use X bar S chart if there are enough data points
Pain interference with life activities.	Patients will be asked to identify how much pain interfered with their enjoyment of life and general activity over the past week	Telephone call (Twice a week) using PEG	Run charts then I-chart average that the participants report that week. Using X bar S chart if there are enough data points
Knowledge related to CLBP and NPIs	Pre and post surveys on knowledge related CLBP and NPIs	Self-report surveys, including Low Back Pain Knowledge Questionnaire (LKQ)	Paired samples t-tests to compare the pre and post-survey data
Attitude/Beliefs related to NPIs	Pre- and post-surveys on attitudes and beliefs related to NPIs.	Survey of Pain Attitudes- Brief Version (SOPA-B)	Paired samples t-Tests to compare the pre and post-survey data
Use of Opioid Medication	Patients will be asked how many opioids pills they used over the past week	Telephone call (Twice a week) to assess the number of opioid pills which will be converted to Morphine Milliequivalents (MMEs)	Run charts then I-chart average of MMEs that were used by the participants bi-weekly

Run charts were graphical representations that showed data organized in an orderly manner to identify non-random changes over time (Provost & Murray, 2011). A random variation noted on a run chart signified an expected routine process. On the other hand, a non-random variation indicated an unexpected change that may not have been seen without the intervention. There were four rules applied for interpreting non-random variations in run charts; the presence of a trend was identified as five or more consecutive points going up or down; a shift of six or more consecutive points above or below the median line, too few or too many runs as well as the presence of an astronomical data point (Provost & Murray, 2011).

The run charts were used in this project to show visual analyses of changes over the two months in which the participants received education and used NPIs. If a non-random variation was noticed, it was an indication of an unexpected change. A limitation of using run charts was the inability to identify the specific reason for a change related to a non-random variation, as it allowed only for detection of change (Provost & Murray). The researcher used additional information to determine the reason the changes occurred.

Control charts were statistical tools that helped to determine if variation in a variable was due to common cause or special cause (Provost & Murray, 2011). Common cause was similar to random variation, and special cause was similar to non-random variation (Provost & Murray, 2011). Control charts were used in QI projects to identify if a change happened, when it happened, and if that change was an improvement (Provost & Murray, 2011). A common cause was an expected change as a result of a process measure, while a special cause was an unexpected change (Provost & Murray, 2011). There were five rules for identifying the special causes, “a single point outside the control limits, eight or more points above or below the UL or the LL, six consecutive points creating a decreasing or increasing trend, two or three consecutive

points in the outer one-third of the upper or lower control limits, and 15 consecutive points close to the centerline” (Provost & Murray, 2011, p. 116). Control limits were statistical sigma limits based on the calculation of the three sigma limits above the average and three sigma limits below the average (Provost & Murray, 2011). The sigma limits were calculated using three standard deviations upper and lower than the mean (Provost & Murray, 2011). The upper and lower limits were used to show variations within the expected or unexpected limits; however, rules for control charts needed to be applied to determine common or special cause variations (Provost & Murray, 2011). The three sigma limits created zones in the inner zone, between the first standard deviation limits, middle zone, between the second standard deviation limits and upper zones, between the third standard deviation limits (Provost & Murray, 2011). The control charts used for this QI project are C-charts and I charts (Table 2 for definitions of C-charts, I charts, and X bar S charts; Provost & Murray, 2011).

Table 2

Definitions for Control and Individual Charts

Term	Definition
C- chart	A type of control chart that is used with count data to identify the number of conformities or non-conformities within a sample.
I-chart	A type of control chart that is used to identify variations due to common and special causes using continuous variable data in one subgroup, such as the measurement of pain.

Data for the 30 participants were entered into separate spreadsheets and automatically plotted to run charts. The data were initially plotted using run charts since there were fewer than 20 data points. Run charts were used to plot data points obtained twice a week from the 30 participants for the self-reported number of NPIs used, pain levels, PEG results, and opioids

used. Once 16 data points were collected, the run charts were converted to control charts (either C chart, I-chart, depending on the variable being measured). The data continued to be collected over eight weeks until six additional data points were accrued, adding up to 16 data points total. At this point, the analysis determined that there was a common cause or special cause variation. Using 16 data points, the analysis was considered a trial limit since 20 data points are recommended for control chart analysis. Trial limits were used to detect preliminary changes in the process and indicated that the intervention affected the variable of interest (Provost & Murray, 2011).

Paired *t*-tests were used to compare the averages of two values (Xu et al., 2017). For this project, paired *t*-tests were used to compare the average for the values of the data obtained from pre- and post-surveys based on self-reported knowledge for low back pain, the attitudes and beliefs of participants at the beginning of the project before receiving the education, and at the end of the project after education was provided. For this project, a descriptive analysis was used to present the types of NPIs used as reported by the participants (Xu et al., 2017).

Results

Sociodemographic Characteristics

Descriptive statistics, frequencies, and percentages were used to analyze participants' sociodemographic characteristics. Thirty patients participated in the project: 24 (80%) females and 6 (20%) males. Five (16.67%) patients were in the age ranges of 25-34, six (20%) were in the 35-44 age range, nine (30%) were 45-54 and 55-64 and one (3.33%) patient was over 75. There were no patients in the age ranges of 18-24 or 65-74 years. Of the 30 patients, 23 (76.67%) reported annual incomes below \$25,200, with 12 (40%) of the patients reporting an income of less than \$9,999, and 11(36%) had an income of \$10,000 to \$24,999. Three (10%) of the patients reported annual incomes of \$25,000 to \$ 49,999, one (3.33%) patient reported an income of \$50,000 to \$74,999, and three (10%) patients preferred not to answer. Of the 30 patients, 15(50%) reported being single, 11(36.67%) were married, 1(3.33%) was widowed, and three 3(10%) were divorced. No patients reported being separated. All patients had reported having some education. For educational level, the most frequently reported among patients was 10 (33.3%) who had high school but no diploma, followed by eight (26.67%) patients with college credits but no degree, five (16.67%) patients had some high school, three (10%) had a bachelor's degree, two (6.67%) had vocational training, and one (3.33%) had a professional degree. Eleven of the patients (36.67%) reported being unable to work. In the category of self-employed and out of work/ looking, one (13.33%) patient, homemaker, full-time employment, and part-time employment each had three (10%) patients, and the out of work/ not looking category had two (6.67%) patients. There were no students or retirees. Of the 30 patients, 11(36.67%) lived with spouses, 12(40.0%) lived with their children, five (16.67%) lived alone,

three (10.0%) lived with others, and three (10%) lived with other people not family-related.

Table 3 presents participants' sociodemographic.

Table 3

Project Demographics

Demographic	<i>n</i>	%
Age		
18-24	0	0
25-34	5	16.67
35-44	6	20
45-54	9	30
55-64	9	30
65-74	0	0
≥75	1	3.33
Marital status		
Single	15	50
Married	11	36.67
Widowed	1	3.33
Divorced	3	10
Separated	0	0
Gender		
Males	6	20
Females	24	80
Education		
No Schooling	0	0
Grade 8	0	0
High School No Diploma	10	33.33
High School Diploma	5	16.67
College Credit, No degree	8	26.67
Vocational training	2	6.67
Associate degree	1	3.33
Bachelor's degree	3	10.00
Master's degree	0	0
Professional degree	1	3.33
Living Arrangements		
Alone	5	16.67
Spouse	10	33.33
Children	12	40.00
Friends	0	0

Roommate	1	3.33
Other	3	10.00
<hr/>		
Demographic	<i>n</i>	%
<hr/>		
Employment		
Self-Employed	4	13.33
Out of work looking	4	13.33
Out of work not looking	2	6.67
Homemaker	3	10.00
Student/Retired	0	0
Unable to work	11	36.67
Full-time Employment	3	10.00
Part-time Employment	3	10.00
<hr/>		
Annual Income		
\$0-\$9,999	12	40.00
\$10,000-\$24,999	11	36.67
\$25,000-\$49,999	3	10.00
\$50,000-\$74,999	1	3.33
\$75,000 or greater	0	0
Prefer not to answer	3	10
<hr/>		

Use of Non-Pharmacological Interventions

There were 11 NPIs used in the project. Patients were able to select any NPI they wanted. The XMR (aka Individuals) Chart showed the time series data obtained on the first contact were regarding their use of NPIs through the sixteenth contact day. Within the project time, data were obtained twice weekly and plotted on the run charts as the number of NPIs used that week and the type of NPI used. The XMR chart for the NPIs showed a signal for special cause variation (a trend) starting from the third contact day, which demonstrated that patients were using more NPIs over the eight weeks of the project (Figure 5). A trend was defined as six or more points increasing consecutively (Provost & Murray, 2011). As a result of this trend, the control limits were recalculated starting at the fifth contact day. During the follow-up calls, the PA encouraged the participants to try other NPIs discussed in the education.

Figure 5
XMR Chart Average NPIs

Run Charts showed similar findings for the individual patient run charts (Appendix I). Out of the 30 patients, 15(50%) showed evidence of non-random variations in their increased use of NPIs. Non-random variations were defined as shifts, trends, and too few or too many runs, numbers of runs, or astronomical points (Provost & Murray, 2011). For the NPI run charts, shifts were identified as six or more consecutive points above the median, trends as five or more consecutive points increasing and fewer than five runs, which were counted as how many times a line crosses the center line (Provost & Murray, 2011). Based on the 16 data points, number of runs less than five or more than 12 indicated non-random variation, according to the rules of run charts (Provost & Murray, 2011). All but one of the patients used more than one NPI by the fifth contact day. Out of the 30 patients, one had increased their use of NPIs by four, and 11 patients were using at least three NPIs. Fourteen patients were using two NPIs, and two patients used one NPI. Twenty-four patients continued to increase their use of NPIs on the fifth contact day. Fifteen of the 24 more than doubled their use of NPIs. Two of the 30 patients decreased their use of NPIs, and four had used the same amount of NPIs from the fifth contact day to the end of the project. Music was the most used NPI. Thirteen patients were using music, 13 used exercises, 10

used meditation, seven used relaxation, eight used hot compress, six used distraction, five used essential oils and massage, three used deep breathing, and one patient used imagery.

Pain Level, Interference with Enjoyment of Life and Interference with General Activity

The *t*-test for the aggregated data results for the PEG tool showed a mean of 8.03 for pre-test and 7.26 for post-test, with a *p*-value of .009, indicating there was overall improvement across the three values on pain level, interference with EOL, and general activity in response to the education and use of NPIs as reported by patients, see Table 4. The results showed significant results for each question. The *p*-value for question one was .049, question two was *p* = .017, and question three was *p* = .024, indicating improvement in pain and pain interference among the patients who participated.

Table 4

Two-Tailed Paired Samples t-Test for NPI Use Between Pre- and Post- Intervention

Aggregate NPI Pre-		Aggregate NPI Post-		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
8.04	1.81	7.26	2.20	2.79	.009	0.51

Note. *N* = 30. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 29. *d* represents Cohen's *d*.

Pain Level

Pain level was obtained from patients on the first contact day, then twice-weekly, and finally on the sixteenth contact day. Data were plotted on run charts, which were converted to control charts with trial limits. Special cause variations were seen in the XMR control charts with pain level (Figure 6). The stated pain scores were below the mean of 8.2; therefore, the control limits were recalculated to assess the change in process. The improvement in pain levels was in response to the pain education and increased use of NPIs.

Figure 6*XMR Chart Average Pain Level*

The run charts for pain level showed similar results for 17(56.67%) of the patients who reported improvement in their pain level (Appendix J). There was evidence of pain level illustrated by non-random variation with shifts, trends, and too few runs. A trend was interpreted as five or more consecutive data points decreasing downwards, and a shift was interpreted as six or more consecutive data points below the center line and fewer than five runs.

Data for pain level was also analyzed using a two-tailed *t*-test to test the differences in the mean scores pre- and post-implementation of the education. The pretest data were taken on the first day of contact with a patient, and the posttest data were collected on the sixteenth day. The data were analyzed using Intellectus™ (Table 5). The mean pain score before interventions was 8.30, and the mean after intervention was 7.80. This was considered statistically significant with a *p*-value of .049.

Table 5

Two-Tailed Paired Samples t-Test for the Difference Between Pre-Pain Level and Post Pain Level

Pre-Pain Level		Post- Pain Level		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
8.30	1.62	7.80	1.95	2.06	.049	0.38

Note. $N = 30$. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 29. *d* represents Cohen's *d*.

Pain Interference with the Enjoyment of Life

Special cause variations were noted in the XMR charts for pain interference with EOL, as indicated by a trend (Figure 7). A trend was interpreted as six consecutive data points decreasing downwards. The special cause variations indicated an improvement in the reduction of pain interference with EOL. As a result of the special cause variation seen, the control limits were adjusted starting with the fifth contact day, illustrating a process change. After the process change, there continued to be evidence of common cause variation, which indicated that the improvement was maintained.

Figure 7

XMR Chart Pain Interference with Enjoyment of Life

The improvement in pain level was supported by the individual run charts (Appendix K).

Out of the 30 patients, 18 (60%) showed non-random variation with decreased pain interference

with EOL, 11 (36.67%) showed non-random variation with increased pain interference with EOL, and 1 (3.33%) showed random variation, indicating no change with pain interference with life enjoyment. Non-random variations were interpreted as shifts, trends, or too few runs.

As with the pain level, data for EOL were analyzed with t-tests using Intellectus (Table 6). Question two on the PEG survey represents the EOL data. The data used for the *t*-test analysis were obtained on the first contact day and the 16th contact day. The above results were supported by the analysis from Intellectus, which showed a mean score of 8.03 before intervention and seven after intervention with a *p*-value of .017, indicating a statistical change in the decrease of pain interference with life enjoyment.

Table 6

Paired Samples t-Test for the Difference Between Pre- and Post- Pain Interference with Enjoyment of Life (PIwEOL)

Pre- PIwEOL		Post- PIwEOL		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
8.03	1.94	7.00	2.57	2.53	.017	0.46

Pain Interference with General Activity

Although there was a slight difference in the patients' reporting between the pain interference with EOL and general activities, the two charts almost mirrored each other. Special cause variations were shown in the XMR control charts for pain interference with general activities (Figure 8). The special cause variations included a trend with more than six consecutive data points decreasing downwards, indicating an improvement in decreased pain interference with general activity. A signal of special cause variation was noted from the third contact day, which demonstrated that pain interference with EOL decreased over the eight weeks

of the project; hence, on the fifth day, control limits were recalculated to indicate a process change.

Figure 8

Pain Interference Activity with General Activity

The improvement was supported by the individual run charts showing that out of the 30 patients, 23 (76.67 %) showed non-random variation for decreased pain interference with general activity, 4 (13.33%) showed non-random variation with an increase in pain interference with general activity, and 3 (10%) showed random variation indicating no change in the pain interference with general activity (Appendix L). Non-random variations were interpreted as shifts, trends, or too few runs (Provost & Murray, 2011).

Data from pain interference with general activity was also analyzed with the paired *t*-tests using Intellectus (Table 7). Question three on the PEG survey represents the data for interference with general activity. The above results from the XMR charts and control charts were supported by the analysis from the paired *t*-tests, which showed a mean score of 7.80 pre-intervention and

6.97 post-intervention with a p -value of .024, indicating a statistical change in a decrease of pain interference with general activity.

Table 7

Paired Samples t-Test for the Difference Between Pre- and Post- Pain Interference with General Activity (PIwGA)

Pretest PIwGA		Posttest PIwGA		t	p	d
M	SD	M	SD			
7.80	2.30	6.97	2.58	2.39	.024	0.44

Note. $N = 30$. Degrees of Freedom for the t -statistic = 29. d represents Cohen's d .

Opiates

On the first contact day, patients were asked to state the number of opiates taken for pain in the past week. After that, every two weeks, including the sixteenth contact day, the number of opiates taken was self-reported and documented in the run charts as MMEs. Data were analyzed as aggregate and as individual values using paired t-tests in the Intellectus™.

The XMR charts for opiates showed a common cause variation, indicating no change in a decrease of opiate use among the patients (Figure 8). Although six data points were hovering within the first sigma lines, 15 data points hovering around the mean are needed to interpret special cause variation. However, a visual decline of the data points at the fifth contact day suggested a decrease in the use of opiates. To analyze this with the rest of the measures, the control limits were recalculated, as was done with the rest of the data. Despite the recalculated control limits, the chart continued to demonstrate common cause variation, indicating no change in process. The observation showed that the number of opiates taken was not overly affected by the interventions of education and NPIs use. The results of the XMR charts were supported by the individual run charts that showed that out of 30 patients, 22(73.3%) showed random

variation, indicating no reduction of opiates taken. Eight (26.6%) patients showed non-random variation with a decrease in opiates taken (Appendix L).

Figure 9

Opiates Taken

Changes in Pain Attitudes

A SOPA was completed before and after receiving the education. The results of the analysis did not show significant differences in a change of pain attitudes before and after implementation of the education (Table 8). There were 30 questions from the SOPA tool, which were analyzed individually and as aggregate data using the paired t-tests. This survey asked, for example, “there are many times when I can influence the amount of pain I feel,” “I will probably always have to take pain medications,” “when I hurt, I want my family to treat me better” (Appendix C). Patients use a Likert scale from zero to four. The data were analyzed using paired sample t-test results as an aggregate and as individual responses. The results showed a mean of 2.26 in the pretest and 2.25 in the posttest with a *p*-value of .886, which indicated no statistical change in patients’ attitudes as a result of the intervention of education (Table 8).

Table 8

Two-Tailed Paired Samples t-Test for the Difference of Pre- and Post-Survey of Pain Attitudes

Aggregate pretest SOPA		Aggregate Posttest SOPA		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
2.26	0.51	2.25	0.63	0.14	.886	0.03

Note. *N* = 30. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 29. *d* represents Cohen's *d*.

Changes in Knowledge of Low Back Pain

Analysis with *t*-tests was done to identify the differences between the aggregate on all 16 questions and for individual questions pre- and post-education implementation. The paired *t*-Test analysis on the aggregate value for all 16 questions analyzed showed a mean of 0.23 pretest and 0.48 posttest with a *p*-value of <.001, indicating significant changes in the knowledge acquired at the beginning and at the end of the project (Table 9).

Table 9

Two-Tailed Paired Samples t-Test for the Difference in Pre- and Post- Low Back Pain

Knowledge Gained

Aggregate pretest LKQ		Aggregate posttest LKQ		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
0.23	0.17	0.48	0.22	-6.10	<.001	1.11

Note. *N* = 30. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 29. *D* represents Cohen's *d*

The results of individual *t*-tests between LKQ the pretest and posttest questions showed significant changes for Questions 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, and 16. The questions evaluated the patients' knowledge on chronic back pain for definition, causes, necessary and unnecessary treatments, and interventions such as medications and NPIs, including diagnostics such as MRI and X-Rays, and what can be done to worsen or alleviate pain. Some of the questions included, "What is chronic low back pain?" "What is sciatica pain?" "These can cause

low back pain,” “What is needed for the diagnosis of low back pain?” (Appendix D). The LKQ tool is valid and reliable (Kovacs et al., 2019). It has been used in clinical settings among different cultures to assess pain (Claus et al., 2017; Kovacs et al., 2019; Rufa et al., 2019). The LKQ was helpful in evaluating the participant’s knowledge of low back pain in this project.

Conclusion

The project used a time series, pretest-post design. Paired t-tests are statistical tools from Intellectus™ used to compare the differences between the mean values for two points that are matched, such as pre-test question one and post-test question two (Hedberg & Ayers, 2015). A benefit of paired t-tests is the interpretation of the differences as significant or non-significant. Significant changes were seen with analysis of pretest-posttest *p*-values for knowledge of back pain was $<.001$, pain level .049, interference of EOL .017, and general activity .024. Non-significant changes were found with pain attitudes and opiates.

The results obtained from the QI Macros® analysis show that among the patients with chronic back pain, there was an increase in the use of NPIs, a decrease in reported pain, pain interference with EOL, and general activities. There were non-significant changes in the reported opiate use or attitudes towards pain. It may be concluded that the interventions of education and the 11 NPIs offered in this project were effective in decreasing pain, pain interference with EOL, and general activities among patients with CLBP. However, the interventions may not have been effective in decreasing opiate use or pain attitudes. Perhaps other strategies or other NPIs may have been more effective. Patients reported no change in opiate use and attitudes towards it.

Discussion

Sociodemographic characteristics of participants included gender, age, marital status, living arrangements, education, employment, and annual income. These demographics were representative of the clinic population. The majority of participants in this project were female, of low socioeconomic status, unemployed, did not graduate high school, and were between 45 and 64 years of age. Older age was a risk factor identified in the literature for CLBP (Fehrmann et al., 2019; NIH, 2020; Wong et al., 2017). Most patients in this project lived with family or friends and were not married.

More women than men participated in the project; previous studies found that more women suffered from CLBP than men (Ahern et al., 2019; Fehrmann et al., 2019) since women have lower muscle mass (Meints et al., 2018). Most of the participants were of low SES and level of education, which was consistent with previous research that found low SES to be associated with CLBP (Ikeda et al., 2019) and a higher level of education was associated with decreased incidence of LBP (Zadro et al., 2017). Higher education was also associated with increased use of NPIs (Lozier et al., 2018).

Marital status and living arrangements provided more opportunities for social support; married patients and those living with others had a social support system established within their home (Benyapa et al., 2018). Patients who were married or living with a friend were found to have more pain relief from their use of NPIs (Benyapa et al., 2018). The HPM predicted that interpersonal and situational influences promote health-promoting behaviors, which appears to be the case in the project (Murdaugh et al., 2019). Additionally, living arrangements can influence a patient's level of self-care management since those who lived alone may not be as

motivated to use NPIs as patients who were living with a spouse or friends (Benyapa et al., 2018).

Non-Pharmacological Interventions

There was a significant increase in the use of NPIs among the participants in the project, specifically on the third contact day. This increase demonstrated that the participants were willing to try NPIs to help resolve their pain (Du et al., 2017; Lozier et al., 2019). Research showed that the use of NPIs does lead to an increase in pain relief (Du et al., 2017; Greenwald & Shafritz, 2018; Furlan et al., 2015; Lozier et al., 2018; Wendt et al., 2019). There was an increase in the use of NPIs from the third contact day of the project among 17 of the patients, indicating that patients significantly used more NPIs over the course of the project with continued communication (Ahern et al., 2019; Benyapa et al., 2018; Mehl-Madrona et al., 2016).

The consistent use of the NPIs among the 17 patients in this project can be attributed to an increase in their knowledge about selecting appropriate NPIs for them (Benyapa et al., 2018; Chou et al., 2017; Chou et al., 2018; Herman et al., 2018; Lozier et al., 2018). Patients may have valued the autonomy of assisting in their own treatment options, thereby also increasing their compliance to the use of an NPI that helped to alleviate their pain (Ahern et al., 2019; Becker et al., 2017; Du et al., 2017; Gardener et al., 2018). Non-pharmacological interventions are non-invasive and non-threatening, which may have increased patients' comfort level in using them (AHNA, 2019; Darnall & Colloca, 2018; Du et al., 2017). They were also easily accessible since they could be used at home without a prescription (AHNA, 2019; Becker et al., 2017; Chou et al., 2017).

On the eleventh contact patient day, the number of NPIs dropped, and the upward trend was broken. Despite the broken trend, the variation remained non-random, which demonstrated

that NPIs were still significantly used. At the time the trend was broken, there was extremely cold weather in the area. Many patients stated during their contact calls that the cold weather made their pain worse, which made them stop using NPIs (Beukenhorst et al., 2020). Despite patients reporting an increase in pain due to the cold weather, this relationship was not supported by research (Beukenhorst et al., 2020).

In this project, patients were contacted twice a week, which may have encouraged them to adhere to the use of NPIs (Ahern et al., 2019; Becker et al., 2018). In the HPM model, this adherence may have been due to the interpersonal influences, which come from others such as HCPs who can influence a patient to comply with a treatment regime (Murdaugh et al., 2019).

Pain Level

Pain level was found to be reduced among 12 out of the 30 patients during the project period. Research has demonstrated that NPIs were effective in decreasing back pain (Chou et al., 2017; De Paolis et al., 2019; Du et al., 2017; Mehl-Madrone et al., 2016). Although NPIs are recommended as the first line of treatment, additional benefits of pain relief have been shown when used as part of a multimodal approach. The combination of pharmacological and NPIs can be used to help patients with CP to manage and cope better (Chenot et al., 2017; Chou et al., 2017; Ikemoto et al., 2018; Maher et al., 2017).

In addition to NPIs, the medication regimen for the patients in the project was continued, which may have increased their use of the NPIs, since they knew it would not impact their access to their pain medication. The patients' attitudes towards NPIs may have become more positive following the pain education offered at the beginning of the project (Ahern et al., 2019; Becker et al., 2017; Benyapa et al., 2017). Pain relief among 12 out of the 30 patients increased between

the third and fourth contact day with no change in their use of NPIs. Research has found use of NPIs provided short-term pain relief, which was demonstrated in this project (Chou et al., 2017).

Pain Interference with Enjoyment of Life and General Activity

The special cause variation findings in the decrease of pain interference with EOL and general activity may have been the result of the effectiveness of the education regarding CLBP. Research was inconsistent on the effect of education and NPIs on GA and EOL. Education was found to increase the EOL, but not GA (Ahern et al., 2019; Mehl-Madrona et al., 2016). On the other hand, education increased EOL and GA (Urits et al., 2019; Vlaeyen et al., 2018, Wendt et al., 2019).

The use of NPIs may have helped participants in this project to cope better with their pain; thus, increasing their EOL and general activity (Urits et al., 2019; Vlaeyen et al., 2018). Moreover, the project was completed before the holiday season, which may have caused the patients to experience more EOL and general activity despite the pain, especially with the help of NPIs. The twice-a-week contact with the patients may have encouraged patients to be more aware of how their pain interfered with their EOL and general activity.

Opiates

There was no significant decrease in the use of opiates, but there was a decrease in the level of pain the patients experienced. Research shows that education helps reduce the use of opiates (Darnall et al., 2018; Mehl-Madrona et al., 2016). In this project, the lack of opiate reduction may be explained by the patients' fear of reporting a decrease in their opiate use for fear of receiving fewer pills or having their prescriptions discontinued (Higgins et al., 2018; Becker et al., 2017). However, there was a decrease in opiate use among eight patients who decreased their use by half. These patients had been taking one pain pill a day, and once they

began to use the NPIs, their use of opiates went down to one every other day and then one every two to three days. The patients' use of NPIs may have helped to relieve their pain enough to no longer need the same level of medication (Mehl-Madrona et al., 2016). The education intervention helped explain how NPIs can decrease the use of opiates (Ahern et al., 2019; Darnall et al., 2018; Mehl-Madrona et al., 2016). These patients also reported positive benefits from using the NPIs (Mehl-Madrona et al., 2016).

Regular long-term opioid use or high doses of opiates has been associated with difficulties in discontinuing (Becker et al., 2017; Higgins et al., 2017; Turner et al., 2016). Although the research found that taking opiates was related to a decrease in EOL and general activity, this project showed that when NPIs were added to patients' treatment regimen, EOL and general activity increased (Di Marco et al., 2019; Turner et al., 2016). The CDC (2018) recommended that providers consider doses less than 50MME/day and avoid doses higher than 90MME/day. In this project, the highest number of MME was 30 daily. The continued use of opiates may also have occurred because patients had taken them regularly for a prolonged period, making them harder to discontinue and causing patients to develop tolerance or dependence. However, it should be noted that no patients in the project asked for more pills (Kaye et al., 2017; NIDA, 2018; Sullivan et al., 2017; Turner et al., 2016).

Change in Pain Attitudes and Beliefs

The results showed no significant change in attitudes towards pain after the completion of the educational intervention. However, pretest data showed that attitudes towards pain were negative as patients tended to believe that their pain level would never decrease, and they would suffer all their lives. This lack of significant change can be attributed to the length of the project. It may have required more than eight weeks to change attitudes, and education alone may not

have been sufficient (Wang et al., 2020). According to the HPM model, negative attitudes can negatively influence health-promoting behaviors, which may decrease participation in the use of NPIs (Murdaugh et al., 2019). It was believed that as patients increased their pain knowledge and use of NPIs, their attitudes towards their pain changed (Becker et al., 2018; Benyapa et al., 2018; Eaton et al., 2018; Mehl-Madrona et al., 2016; Vanhaudenhuyse et al., 2017). There was a high use of NPIs among participants in this project, which may have been due to the education and not due to attitude change (Murdaugh et al., 2019).

Change in Low Back Pain Knowledge

There was a significant change in knowledge regarding pain after the completion of the educational intervention. Through the education, patients gained insight into their condition, which helped them understand their pain (Darnall et al., 2018; Louw et al., 2019). Increasing patients' knowledge of NPIs and the effectiveness of treating CLBP may have decreased their skepticism about their efficacy (Becker et al., 2018; Higgins et al., 2017). The educational intervention may have helped patients understand that an increase in pain was not an indication of a worsening condition but merely normal fluctuations in pain level (Allegri et al., 2016; Darnall & Colloca, 2018; Darnall et al., 2018; Hartvigsen et al., 2018; Louw et al., 2019; Murdaugh et al., 2019; Nijs et al., 2015; Urits et al., 2019). Louw et al. (2019) found that increased knowledge on CLBP reduced pain among the patients with CLBP.

Strengths and Limitations

This pre- and post-QI project utilized a well-planned interventional design that successfully addressed its purpose (Alessandri et al., 2017). The design was strong because it delivered noninvasive interventions as well as provided patient education, which was understandable and easy to use. The use of NPIs and education was followed and compared to

pain interference with quality of life, pain level, and use of opioids. Additionally, using QI Macros to analyze the results allowed for tracking the progress of NPI use (Provost & Murray, 2011). Data analyses increased the accuracy of data interpretation since there were statistical estimates of the direction of the data (Provost & Murray, 2011). The project recruited 30 participants without attrition. There was continuous communication with the patients in which they noted that they felt highly cared for during the project.

The literature review was extensive and synthesized the available research regarding CLBP and NPIs, which was also included in the pain education. The HPM was used successfully to guide the project due to its prediction of the factors that influenced a patient's plan for engaging in health-promoting behaviors. Factors that may have influenced the patients' decisions to increase NPIs and reduce their opiates may have been their increased knowledge of LBP and NPIs. Additionally, they obtained pain relief as demonstrated by decreased pain interference with GA and EOL, which may have been viewed as benefits to action (Murdaugh et al., 2019; Pender, 2011; Pender et al., 2015). Interpersonal influences related to the provider-patient relationship, living arrangements, or marital status may have influenced the positive results (Murdaugh et al., 2019; Pender, 2011; Pender et al., 2015).

The project was conducted over eight weeks, which limited the data collection. Most similar projects were conducted over four months to a year (Chou et al., 2017; Vanhauzenhuysen et al., 2017, Wang et al., 2020). This limitation may have influenced some of the results. Results may also have been influenced by social desirability bias in that the patients may have responded positively to the education to please the PA (Latkin et al., 2017). The PA was the healthcare provider for some participants, which may have skewed the results in a positive direction (Latkin et al., 2017). Additionally, the project had a small sample, which may not have been

representative of the population at the project clinic, although demographic data were consistent with the literature.

The project's design may have caused a pretest/posttest effect in which patients recalled their responses during the pretest and made sure to change their responses during the posttest (Alessandri et al., 2017). Additionally, the project relied on self-reported data, which was subjective and difficult to verify, leading to an exaggeration of symptoms and were subject to memory lapses by patients (Mehl-Madrona et al., 2016). When participants could not be reached on a contact day, they were asked to reflect on the day that was missed and report their pain level. This may have caused recall bias, where patients may only recall the positive information (Althubaiti, 2016). Finally, the findings of this project may lack generalizability since this project was conducted at one clinic with a small sample that may not represent national statistics.

Future Implications

The project proposed future implications in the treatment of CLBP. Providers should use NPIs as their first intervention method prior to prescribing opiates (Eaton et al., 2018, CDC, 2016). Ongoing communication between the provider and patients was needed to help patients better cope with their pain (Lozier et al., 2018). Education may have helped decrease pain among CLBP patients by discussing the neurological basis for their pain and its functions (Greenwald & Shafritz, 2018). The educational program should be integrated into routine care, which may help change patients' attitudes towards pain, leading to decreased pain levels (Vanhaudenhuyse et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2020). Establishing a trusting relationship between the patient and providers is important in encouraging NPI use (Ahern et al., 2019). The PCPs should manage patients with CLBP because they have an established relationship that can encourage their patients to use NPIs (Darnall et al., 2018; Eaton et al., 2018; Henry et al., 2018). Future QI projects should include a

larger sample that would be more representative of various patients' demographic characteristics with CLBP to increase generalizability (Matheve et al., 2020; Michalsen et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2019). In addition to the clinic in San Bernardino, other clinics should be encouraged to modify their protocols for the management and treatment of CLBP and include an educational program, NPIs, and use CDC-based guidelines (CDC, 2016). The NPIs should consist of the EBP toolkit (AHNA, 2019). Patients should receive a wide variety of self-administered NPIs, which increases their options for self-care (Ahern et al., 2019; Du et al., 2017; Lozier et al., 2018).

Conclusion

Chronic low back pain is an unpleasant sensation that lasts more than three months. Healthcare providers should be sensitive to the needs of patients who live with CP. Chronic pain has been associated with depression, anxiety, and insomnia, worsening pain, and disability. Educating patients about the role of neuroscience in the development and maintenance of CP helps them understand that pain is not indicative of worsening conditions to the lower back. Thus, a holistic approach should be applied in the treatment of CLBP. The HPM was useful in this project in guiding the PA in treating patients with CLBP. Education helped to decrease pain, PIwEOL, and PIwGA. Engaging in desirable activities may offer a distraction from the pain, thereby decreasing pain level (Lemmon & Hampton, 2018, Wendt et al., 2019). The activities may also have relieved the pain due to stretching the muscles (Lemmon & Hampton, 2018). Increasing NPI use helped the patient control their pain and increase their autonomy in controlling their own health and managing their CLBP.

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APPENDIX A

Authorization Letter to Conduct Project

Urgent *Family* Care**Gospha G. Campbell, MD. Inc**
Board Certified in Family Medicine

June 23, 2019

To: The Institutional Review Board at California State University Fullerton

Project Author Name: Millicent Muthike

Title of Research: EXPLORING NON-OPIOID ALTERNATIVES OF CHRONIC PAIN
MANAGEMENT

I, Dr Campbell, give Millicent Muthike permission to conduct her DNP project at the Urgent Family Care, 1850 South Waterman Ave, Suite F, San Bernardino, CA 92408. The title of the project is EXPLORING NON-OPIOID ALTERNATIVES OF CHRONIC PAIN MANAGEMENT. I give her full access to the patients attending the clinic for opioid refills in treatment for their chronic pain. I am aware that the project will involve providing educational information in the form of a pamphlet. I give her permission to distribute the pamphlet to the patients who agree to participate in her project. I understand that participation in her project will be voluntary and patients will have the opportunity to opt out at any time.

Please feel free to contact me should IRB members need more information, please contact me directly at 909-890-9393.

Sincerely,

DR. GOSPHA CAMPBELL, MD

APPENDIX B

Patient Consent for Participation

California State University, Fullerton, Research Study Consent Form

Study Title: Development of a Patient Education Program: Non-Pharmacological Interventions for Management of Chronic Back Pain

Protocol Number: HSR-20-21-86

Researchers: Millicent Muthike, MSN, FNP-C
Manal Alatrash, PhD, RN
Laura Sarff, DNP, RN, MBA, CPHQ, NEA-BC

You are being asked to take part in a quality improvement project carried out by Millicent Muthike, MSN, RN FNP-C, Manal Alatrash, PhD, RN and Laura Sarff, DNP, RN, MBA, CPHQ, NEA-BC. This consent form explains the project and your part in it if you decide to join the study. Please read the form carefully, taking as much time as you need. Ask the researcher to explain anything you do not understand. You can decide not to join the study. If you join the study, you can change your mind later and leave the study at any time. There will be no penalty or loss of services or benefits if you decide not to take part in the study.

What is this study about?

This quality improvement project is being conducted to increase knowledge of chronic low back pain and non-pharmacological interventions and to encourage the use of non-pharmacological interventions to decrease pain, increase physical activity and reduce opioid use in the treatment of back pain. Non-pharmacological interventions are alternative choices used instead of medications used to relieve pain.

You are being asked to take part because you are 18 years and older, with chronic low back pain, are using opioids for the treatment of your pain, and you have seen at this clinic before.

You cannot take part in this study if you are under 18years, have chronic low back pain due to cancer, have chronic pain not related to low back pain, are not using opioids, or do not speak English

Taking part in the study will take about 20-30 minutes.

What will I be asked to do if I am in this study?

If you take part in the study, you will be asked to read and sign the consent form, will be provided with a description of the project and its purposes, and your rights will be discussed (see attached).

You will be asked to provide baseline data, such as age, gender, education level, employment, marital status, living arrangements, and annual income.

You will be asked to fill out a questionnaire on chronic low back pain knowledge. You will also be asked to fill surveys on pain, attitudes, and beliefs related to chronic low back pain and non-pharmacological interventions while you are waiting to see the healthcare provider for your visit. It will take you about 15 minutes to complete the surveys and the questionnaire. You may refuse to answer any questions in the surveys.

You will be asked to stay an extra 20-30 minutes after your visit to be provided with the educational intervention on chronic low back pain and non-pharmacological interventions, and a patient pain tool kit where you can find more information. You will be encouraged to ask questions.

After the initial visit, you will be contacted by the project author twice a week via telephone or by text message, depending on your preference. The purpose of the follow-up contact will be to assess the types of non-pharmacological interventions used, pain level, how pain has interfered with your enjoyment of life and general activities, and the number of opioid pills taken that week. The twice-weekly data collection will continue for eight weeks. During the twice-weekly calls, you will be encouraged to try at least one non-pharmacological intervention. If you have not practiced any non-pharmacological interventions and your pain levels are not changing, you will be given an additional doctor's appointment to evaluate your needs.

At the end of the project, you will be asked to fill out a post-intervention survey about pain, knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs after eight weeks, project when you return to refill your opioid prescriptions.

Patients receiving services through pain management will also be further consulted to determine whether the services were used. The use of non-pharmacological interventions will further be encouraged during this consultation.

The surveys and data collected will be stored by the project author in a locked cabinet located in the project author's office, who will be the only one with access to it. The data will be stored in a password-protected computer only known to the project author.

After analyzing the project data to obtain results, a set of recommendations related to patient education about non-pharmacological interventions and opioids will be developed as a protocol to be followed by all the healthcare providers at the clinic to ensure consistency and sustainability.

Are there any benefits to me if I am in this study?

The potential benefits to you for taking part in this project are: increase use of non-pharmacological interventions, decrease in chronic low back pain, a decrease in pain interference with life enjoyment and general activities, reduction in the number of opioids medication taken for pain, increase in positive attitudes and beliefs towards non-pharmacological interventions as the treatment of chronic low back pain.

If you take part in this project, you may help others in the future to increase the use of non-pharmacological interventions and decrease their pain.

Are there any risks to me if I am in this study?

The potential risks from taking part in this study are psychological stress associated with memory of previous management of pain. Participants will be encouraged to ask questions and verbalize their feelings. Participants who may experience distress as a result of participating in the project will be referred to a crisis hotline, 1-888-743-1478, in the city of San Bernardino.

Will my information be kept anonymous or confidential?

The data for this study are being collected anonymously. Neither the researcher(s) nor anyone else will be able to link data to you. No identifying demographic information will be collected. The pre- and post-surveys will be administered and numbered based on the order in which they will be received. To follow up with participants for the required data collection during the project, and to keep them anonymous, a number will be assigned to each participant during pre-intervention data collection. All information will be kept confidential and stored on a password-protected laptop kept in the project author's locked office. The Project author will place the signed consent form in an envelope that will be stored in a locked cabinet in the locked project author's office. The data for this study will be kept for three years. The results of this study and that the results of the project will be reported collectively.

Are there any costs or payments for being in this study?

There will be no costs to you for taking part in this study.

Who can I talk to if I have questions?

If you have questions about this project or the information in this form, please contact the project author Millicent Muthike at [REDACTED] or e-mail mmuthike@csu.fullerton.edu

If you have questions about your rights as a quality improvement project participant or would like to report a concern or complaint about this project, please contact the Institutional Review Board at (657) 278-7719 or e-mail irb@fullerton.edu

What are my rights as a quality improvement project volunteer?

Your participation in this quality improvement project is completely voluntary. You may choose not to be a part of this project. There will be no penalty to you if you choose not to take part. You may choose not to answer specific questions or to stop participating at any time.

What does my signature on this consent form mean?

Your signature on this form means that:

- You understand the information given to you in this form
- You have been able to ask the researcher questions and state any concerns
- The researcher has responded to your questions and concerns
- You believe you understand the research study and the potential benefits and risks that are involved.

Statement of Consent

I have carefully read and/or I have had the terms used in this consent form and their significance explained to me. By signing below, I agree that I am at least 18 years of age and agree to participate in this project. You will be given a copy of this signed and dated consent form to keep.

Name of Participant (please print) _____

Signature of Participant _____ Date _____

Signature of Investigator _____ Date _____

APPENDIX C

Pain Relief and Self-Care Toolkit

*Holistic Nurses***PAIN RELIEF TOOLS FOR PATIENTS & SELF-CARE**

“First, treat the person. Second, treat the pain.”

Holistic nursing has healing the whole person as its goal. We...

- ③ Care deeply for people and advocate for their rights and choices¹
- ③ Interact with the whole person, not just the illness, trauma, or tasks to be accomplished¹
- ③ Develop our healing presence so we can see, hear, and empathize clearly¹
- ③ Use skilled communication to determine the person's needs^{2,3}
- ③ Provide care that promotes comfort and healing, knowing the results are not always predictable^{1,4}
- ③ Encourage the person to participate in their pain management as much as possible^{5,6}
- ③ Use a multi-faceted approach that includes deep breathing, hydration and movement^{5,6}
- ③ Embrace self-awareness and recognize our own humanity in the experience of our clients¹

Relaxation

Deep Breathing: Instructions: 1) Slowly inhale, imagining you are softening and opening to receive safety, love or peace. 2) Slowly exhale, imagining you are releasing your pain, stress or fear. 3) Practice for short periods. For best results, combine with another intervention.^{1, 7-10}

Note: Some people have experienced prior physical or psychological trauma which may be a significant contributor to their present experience of pain. In these cases, the person may be reluctant to relax because doing so may increase their flashbacks, panic or other PTSD-like symptoms. **Instructions:** 1) If a person is experiencing these symptoms, use your calm, healing presence to help them become mentally and physically grounded in their present situation. 2) Offer PMR (below) instead of Deep Breathing, and refer the person to a specialist who can better serve them.^{1,10}

Progressive Muscle Relaxation (PMR): PMR involves focusing awareness on the body and alternately tightening and relaxing the muscle groups *without* holding the breath. **Instructions:** 1) Begin with the feet and calves: contract those muscles for 5 – 10 seconds or until mild fatigue is felt. 2) Release the tension. 3) Continue upwards through the body to include all muscle groups. 4) Finish with the facial muscles.¹

Meditation & Imagery

Meditation: Meditation can be done while sitting, lying or walking, and there are many ways to meditate. Here is one way.

Instructions: 1) With each inhalation, focus on one personally meaningful word, such as, Faith, Hope, Love or Healing. 2) With each exhalation, focus on that same word softening your awareness and opening it to feel more peace. When your mind strays from your one word, gently bring it back.

3) Practice 10-30 minutes one or more times.^{1,11}

Imagery: Imagery is the use of relaxation and mental visualization to improve well-being.

Instructions: 1) Choose one of the Relaxation tools and practice it for 1-2 minutes. 2) Scan your body and imagine gathering your pain into a ball. 3) Imagine changing the ball's size: first make it larger, then make it smaller. Repeat this several times so you feel confident in your ability. 4) Let's see how small you can make the ball. Is it possible to make it the size of a grain of sand? 5) Using your exhalations, allow the ball to move out of your body. Move it farther away with each exhalation. 6) Rest.¹³⁻¹⁶

Distraction

Distraction has been shown to significantly reduce mild pain; be cost-effective; have little or no negative effects and be more effective when used with other approaches. **Instructions:** Invite your patients to walk around the unit, look out the windows, connect with other patients, etc.^{1,56-58}

All of the above nursing interventions are evidence-based.

For References go to www.AHNA.org/holistic-pain-tools

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AMERICAN
*Holistic
Nurses*
ASSOCIATION

Heat

Heat is a safe and effective treatment for:

- Aching pains, such as from fibromyalgia, over-exertion of muscles, and other chronic pain conditions
- Cramping or spasm pains, such as menstrual pain and low-back pain

Heat causes the blood vessels to dilate, bringing more circulation to the area. **Instructions: 1)** Heat can be applied in the form of a grain-filled bag, a heat pad, deep-heat cream, hot water bottle or heat lamp.

The item should be warm, not hot. **If excessive heat is applied, there is a risk of burns**, so place a cloth between the heat source and the skin for protection. **2)** The skin must be checked at regular intervals. Heat can be re-applied after an hour if needed. Heat has a greater effect when it is combined with gentle exercise or ROM. ²⁷⁻³⁰

Cold

Cold is used in the first 48 hours after soft tissue injury if there is swelling and later rehabilitation.

Instructions: 1) If the skin is broken, protect the area with a plastic bag to protect it then place the ice pack over the plastic bag. Ice can cause frostbite if the skin is not protected or it is left on too long. **2)** Check the skin color after 5 minutes. **3)** If the skin is bright pink or red, STOP. **4)** If it is not bright pink or red, replace the ice for 5-15 minutes. Leaving ice on for too long can slow the healing process. **5)** Re-apply after an hour if needed ²⁷⁻³⁰

PRECAUTIONS: Do not use heat or cold...

- With diabetes or infection
- On areas with poor sensation
- On areas with poor circulation
- Around the front or side of the neck
- On the left shoulder with a heart condition
- When the client cannot follow your directions

All of these pain relief methods are recognized as nursing practice. Refer to your state nurse practice act and the ANA's *Holistic Nursing: Scope and Standards of Practice* for clarity. Check facility policies before implementation. *Pain Relief Tools for Patients & Self-Care* is copyrighted, so the text can not be edited, but duplication and free distribution are encouraged. These instructions are not intended as professional advice for a specific patient. Readers should consult a health professional in matters relating to his/her health and particularly with respect to any symptoms that may require diagnosis or medical attention.

Massage

Comforting Massage is an effective pain relieving intervention but efficacy varies by individual and by cause of pain. **Instructions: 1)** Using a lotion or natural food-grade vegetable oil, slowly and mindfully stroke both sides of the

person's hands, feet, neck, back or shoulders. **2)** Watch the person's face and breathing and for signs of tension to match your pressure to their sensitivity. **3)** For enhanced benefit, encourage the person to use **deep breathing** technique as described above. ^{1,33-39}

Lavender Essential Oil

Lavender Essential Oil has relaxing and pain-reducing capacity but efficacy will vary by individual and by root cause of pain.

Instructions: 1) Make a 1-5% dilution, which is 1-5 drops (0.05 to 0.25 ml) of pure essential oil in 5 ml of natural food-grade carrier such as coconut oil. **2)** Apply mixture to the palms. **3)** Cup palms over the nose and breathe deeply. **4)** Apply the oil mixture topically only on unbroken skin. **Note: Some people are allergic to lavender, so test for sensitivity on a small patch of skin prior to topical use.** Use a 1% dilution for infants and persons who are weak or fragile. ^{1,40-49}

Music

Music stimulates relaxation, distraction and mood alteration which all can help reduce many types of pain. Active participation in music enjoyment, such as occurs in music therapy, is even more effective than passive listening. **Instructions: 1)**

Encourage the person to listen to a wide variety of music they enjoy. **2)** Invite the person into active participation by using Deep Breathing, Imagery, Range of Motion and/or Expressive Movement with their listening and/or by sharing what they are experiencing. ^{1,19-26}

Laughter

Laughter has been proven to relax muscles, produce endorphins, boost immunity, lower stress hormones and decrease pain. Laughing with others produces more powerful effects than laughing alone. ⁶⁰⁻⁶²

All of the above nursing interventions are evidence-based.

For References go to www.AHNA.org/Holistic-Pain-Tools

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APPENDIX D**Demographic Survey****Gender: what is your gender?**

- Male
- Female

Age: What is your age?

- 18-24 years old
- 25-34 years old
- 35-44 years old
- 45-54 years old
- 55-64 years old
- 65-74 years old
- 75 + years old

Education: What is the highest degree or level of school you have completed? (If you're currently enrolled in school, please indicate the highest degree you have *received*.)

- No schooling completed
- Nursery school to 8th grade
- Some high school, no diploma
- High school graduate, diploma or the equivalent (for example GED)
- Some college credit, no degree
- Trade/technical/vocational training
- Associate degree
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Professional degree
- Doctorate degree

Marital Status: What is your marital status?

- Single, never married
- Married or domestic partnership
- Widowed
- Divorced
- Separated

Living arrangements: Do you live (with)

Alone

Spouse

Children

Friends

Roommate

Other relatives: -----

Employment Status: Are you currently...?

- Self-employed
- Out of work and looking for work
- Out of work but not currently looking for work
- A homemaker
- A student
- Military
- Retired
- Unable to work
- Employed full time (40 or more hours per week)
- Employed part-time (up to 39 hours per week)

Annual Income:

- \$0
- \$1 to \$9 999
- \$10 000 to \$24 999
- \$25 000 to 49 999
- \$50 000 to 74 999
- \$75 000 to 99 999
- \$100 000 to 149 999
- \$150 000 and greater
- Prefer not to answer

APPENDIX E

Low Back Knowledge Questionnaire-LKQ

The purpose of this questionnaire is to evaluate your knowledge of low back pain. Mark the correct or incorrect alternative according to each question, if you don't know the answer, mark the option "I don't know."

1. In regards to the general anatomy of the spinal column, mark ONE incorrect alternative:

- a. It has the cervical, thoracic and lumbar vertebrae and the sacrum.
- b. Between each vertebra, there is an intervertebral disc that acts as a "shock absorber."
- c. The vertebrae form a canal through which the spinal cord passes.
- d. The back and abdominal muscles have no function in supporting the spinal column.
- e. I don't know.

2. What is low back pain? Mark ONE correct alternative:

- a. pain located between the lowest ribs and the pelvis
- b. pain between the lowest ribs and the pelvis that radiates down the leg to the foot
- c. pain in any region of the back, from the neck to the hip
- d. pain in the abdomen, lower part of the pelvis or kidneys
- e. I don't know.

3. What is acute low back pain? Mark ONE correct alternative:

- a. pain in the lumbar region that usually improves in three weeks, with or without treatment
- b. untreatable pain in the lumbar region
- c. pain in the lumbar region requiring surgery
- d. pain in the lumbar region lasting more than 3 months
- e. I don't know.

- 4. What is chronic low back pain? Mark ONE correct alternative:**
- a. pain in the lumbar region that usually improves in three weeks, with or without treatment
 - b. untreatable pain in the lumbar region
 - c. pain in the lumbar region requiring surgery
 - d. pain in the lumbar region lasting more than 3 months
 - e. I don't know.
- 5. What is sciatica pain? Mark ONE correct alternative:**
- a. pain located between the lowest ribs and the pelvis
 - b. pain between the lowest ribs and the pelvis that radiates to the leg down to the foot
 - c. pain in any region of the back, from the neck to the hip
 - d. pain in the abdomen, lower part of the pelvis or kidneys
 - e. I don't know.
- 6. These can cause low back pain. Mark TWO correct alternatives:**
- a. cold and aging
 - b. postural problems, arthrosis and a herniated disc
 - c. tumors, infections and fractures
 - d. diabetes
 - e. I don't know.
- 7. These are symptoms of low back pain. Mark TWO correct alternatives:**
- a. a cough, sluggishness and loss of energy
 - b. tiredness and pain throughout the body
 - c. pain in the lumbar region that worsens when carrying weight
 - d. difficulty in picking up objects from the floor
 - e. I don't know.

8. What is needed for the diagnosis of low back pain? Mark TWO correct alternatives:

- a. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and computerized tomography (CT scan) are always needed.
- b. An x-ray is not always needed.
- c. The diagnosis is often possible through the medical history and physical exam of the patient without the need of supplementary exams.
- d. laboratory tests such as glycemia, cholesterol and urine are always needed.
- e. I don't know.

9. In regards to drug treatment for low back pain, mark ONE incorrect alternative:

- a. Anti-inflammatory medicines and analgesics may be used during acute crises.
- b. Corticosteroids may be necessary during an acute crisis.
- c. Antidepressants and anticonvulsants may be used for chronic low back pain.
- d. Topical medications such as gel, plasters or ointments are always indicated.
- e. I don't know.

10. In regards to the treatment for acute low back pain. Mark TWO correct alternatives:

- a. One week of absolute bed rest is indicated.
- b. Definitive sick leave from work is indicated.
- c. Low back pain may improve even without treatment.
- d. The least possible rest is indicated.
- e. I don't know.

11. What can be used to treat chronic low back pain? Mark TWO correct alternatives:

- a. the long-term use of anti-inflammatory medicines
- b. instructions on spine protection and exercises
- c. abdominal supportive belt when performing heavy-duty activities
- d. Physical means such as short waves, ultra-sound, and Bier's oven which are more important than oriented physical exercises.
- e. I don't know.

12. In regards to physical activity and low back pain, mark ONE incorrect alternative:

- a. Walking three times a week for an hour can improve chronic low back pain.
- b. Intensive exercises are indicated for acute low back pain.
- c. Aquatic activities may be beneficial to the patient with chronic low back pain.
- d. The most highly recommended exercises are strengthening of the abdomen and the back muscles, stretching and physical conditioning.
- e. I don't know.

13. To protect the spine, mark TWO correct alternatives:

- a. The best way to sleep is on your stomach.
- b. Sit down to put on your socks and shoes.
- c. Pick up objects from the floor without bending your knees.
- d. Wash the dishes with your stomach leaning against the sink.
- e. I don't know.

14. Again, in relation to spinal protection, mark ONE incorrect alternative:

- a. You should get out of bed carefully, turning sideways with the help of our hands.
- b. Avoid carrying too much weight on one side of the body (divide the load between both arms).
- c. Avoid twisting of the spine.
- d. Wear high heels all day.
- e. I don't know.

15. In regards to acute low back pain, mark TWO correct alternatives:

- a. The great majority of patients recover in three weeks.
- b. After recovery and improvement of the pain, the patient is cured and there is no risk of further crises.
- c. Instructions on how to protect the spine are only important during the crisis.
- d. The orientations for spine protection and energy conservation should be routine in patients with a history of low back pain because relapses are frequent.
- e. I don't know.

16. In regards to surgical treatment for low back pain, mark TWO correct alternatives:

- a. It is indicated in few cases.
- b. It may be important in cases with nerve root compression and spinal column instability that do not improve with clinical treatment.
- c. Surgery guarantees the cure of low back pain.
- d. It is the best treatment for any type of low back pain
- e. I don't know.

APPENDIX F

The Survey of Pain Attitudes-Brief (SOPA-B)

Indicate how true each statement is for you. Circle one number for each statement. Respond to all items. Use the following scale as a guide:0=Very untrue1=Somewhat untrue2=Neither true nor untrue (or does not apply)3=Somewhat true4=Very true

	Very untrue	Somewhat untrue	<i>N</i>	Somewhat true	Very true
1. There are many times when I can influence the amount of pain I feel	0	1	2 3		4
2. I will probably always have to take pain medications	0	1	2 3		4
3. When I hurt, I want my family to treat me better	0	1	2 3		4
4. I do not expect a medical cure for my pain	0	1	2 3		4
5. I have had the most relief from the pain with the use of medications	0	1	2 3		4
6. Anxiety increases the pain I feel	0	1	2 3		4
7. When I am hurting, people should treat me with care and concern	0	1	2 3		4
8. I have given up my search for the complete elimination of my pain through the work of the medical profession	0	1	2 3		4
9. It is the responsibility of my loved ones to help me when I feel pain	0	1	2 3		4
10. Stress in my life increases my pain	0	1	2 3		4
11. Exercise and movement are good for my pain problem	0	1	2 3		4
12. Just by concentrating or relaxing, I can 'take the edge' off my pain	0	1	2 3		4
13. Medicine is one of the best treatments for chronic pain	0	1	2 3		4
14. My family needs to learn how to take better care of me when I am in pain	0	1	2 3		4
15. Depression increases the pain I feel	0	1	2 3		4

16. If I exercise, I could make my pain problem much worse	0	1	2 3	4
17. I believe that I can control how much pain I feel by changing my thoughts	0	1	2 3	4
18. Often I need more tender loving care than I am now getting when I am in pain	0	1	2 3	4
19. Something is wrong with my body which prevents much movement or exercise	0	1	2 3	4
20. I have learned to control my pain	0	1	2 3	4
21. I trust that the medical profession can cure my pain	0	1	2 3	4
22. I know for sure I can learn to manage my pain	0	1	2 3	4
23. My pain does not stop me from leading a physically active life	0	1	2 3	4
24. My physical pain will never be cured	0	1	2 3	4
25. There is a strong connection between my emotions and my pain level	0	1	2 3	4
26. I can do nearly everything as well as I could before I had a pain problem	0	1	2 3	4
27. If I do not exercise regularly, my pain problem will continue to get worse	0	1	2 3	4
28. Exercise can decrease the amount of pain I experience	0	1	2 3	4
29. I'm convinced that there is no medical procedure that will help my pain	0	1	2 3	4
30. My pain would stop anyone from leading an active life	0	1	2 3	4

APPENDIX G**Permission to use Survey of Pain Attitudes Brief Version (SOPA-B)****License Details**

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APPENDIX I

Run Charts NPIs

APPENDIX J

Pain Level Run Chart

APPENDIX K

Pain Interference with Enjoyment of Life

Patient #27

APPENDIX L

Pain Interference with General Activity

